

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

**SUstainable Management of soil Organic Matter to
MItigate Tradeoffs between C sequestration and nitrous
oxide, methane and nitrate losses**

Deliverable D5.2 and D5.3

Test of the fuzzy-expert system to Italian pedoclimatic conditions based on IPCC guidelines for national GHG inventories: trade-off analysis and best management practices.

Due date of deliverable: M48

Actual submission date: 31.01.2024

Acronym: Σ OMMIT

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2021

Project duration: 36 Months

Topic: CM8

Project type: Medium-sized project

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DELIVERABLE
NUMBER: D-WP5.2 and D-WP5.3

DELIVERABLE
TITLE: Test of the fuzzy-expert system to Italian pedoclimatic conditions based on IPCC guidelines for national GHG inventories: trade-off analysis and best management practices.

DELIVERABLE
TYPE: Technical report

WORK PACKAGE N: WP5

WORK PACKAGE
TITLE: Tradeoffs and synergies synthesis: best practices, critical thresholds, indicators

DELIVERABLE
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List of Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Description
WP	Work Package
C	Carbon
GHG	Greenhouse gases
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NO ₃ N	Nitrate nitrogen
CS	Agronomic case scenario
Σi	Σ ommit index
T-Ocs	Trade-off components

1. Introduction

1.1. Aim of this report

This report highlights the accomplishments of WP5 in two key areas:

- Developing a dataset comprising nearly 2 million of agronomic case scenarios to address data gaps emerged from other WPs. These scenarios represent unique combinations of farming practices under prevalent Italian pedo-climatic conditions and are associated with values for soil organic carbon changes (Δ SOC), N_2O emissions, NO_3-N leaching, and crop yield.
- Achieving the final structure of the Σ ommit index, a composite indicator designed to quantify trade-offs among Δ SOC, N_2O emissions, NO_3-N leaching, and yield across diverse agro-environments.

The primary objectives of this report are to:

- Offer a comprehensive documentation outlining the step-by-step process used to construct the case scenario dataset, essential for powering the fuzzy-based trade-off index and effectively addressing data gap.
- Provide an in-depth analysis of the finalized Σ ommit index structure, which has notably evolved since the initial proposal. This analysis will encompass an extensive workflow examination of the fuzzy-expert system application phases, along with an assessment of system performances across diverse agro-environments to identify optimal agricultural management strategies.
- Present the findings from a sensitivity analysis conducted to evaluate the adaptability of the index to changes in the weights of the single trade-off components, aiming to reflect the perspectives of different stakeholders, each with distinct economic, productivity, and sustainability priorities.
- Introduce the Σ ommit Trade-offs analysis dashboard: a user-friendly, web-based interface designed for exploring the case-scenario dataset, observing trends in trade-off components, and accessing associated Σ ommit index values.

1.2. Background

Achieving the objectives set by the Paris Agreement mandates maintaining a balance between anthropogenic GHG (greenhouse gas) sources and sinks to ensure that global temperatures rise remains well below a 2 °C compared to pre-industrial levels (United Nations, 2015). Agricultural management practices such as soil tillage, fertilization, irrigation, crop selection, and residue management can significantly impact GHG emissions. While many studies have focused on the individual effects of these practices (Beillouin et al., 2023; Fohrafellner et al., 2023, Shukla et al., 2019), a comprehensive framework capturing their combined impact on crop productivity, GHG emissions, and water quality across diverse pedoclimatic conditions is yet to materialize.

Legislation governing agricultural GHG mitigation policies demands a quantitative assessment of the co-benefits and trade-offs entwined with adopting alternative management strategies. Unravelling these interactions is crucial, as they could counterbalance the advantages linked with augmented SOC (soil organic carbon) storage (McDonald et al., 2021). Directly estimating these effects on a large scale demands considerable time and resources (Badagliacca et al., 2017; Tirol-Padre et al., 2014). Alternative methods encompass employing agro-ecosystem models at varying spatial and temporal scales. However, such simulation models hinge on extensive data and expertise, potentially limiting their widespread application (Oertel et al., 2016). A more generalized approach involves estimating these effects by

amalgamating equations and emission factors from existing meta-analyses and guidelines currently adopted by European agencies responsible for drafting GHG emission reports (Leip, 2010; Lokupitiya and Paustian, 2006).

Within this report, we delineate the methodological workflow employed to construct the final version of the Σ ommit index (Σ_i), a versatile and adaptable trade-off assessment system intended for use across a spectrum of pedo-climatic and agronomic conditions. The Σ_i is a composite index which uses a fuzzy-logic based process to aggregate four trade-off components: Δ SOC (SOC changes), direct and indirect N_2O emissions, NO_3-N leaching, and crop yield.

In contrast to the rigid binary nature of Boolean logic, fuzzy logic allows for the interpretation of variables as continuous, offering a nuanced assessment that captures the uncertainties and subjectivity inherent in evaluating complex agricultural systems (Amini et al., 2020a; Zrobek et al., 2020). Indeed, agriculture sustainability is a multifaceted concept whose evaluation demands a more human-like reasoning approach, an area where fuzzy logic excels due to its adeptness in handling the concept of partial truth.

The flexibility of the fuzzy logic approach makes it ideal for constructing composite indices, facilitating the contemporary evaluation of multiple interacting variables. Leveraging natural language expressions like 'very good' or 'bad,' fuzzy logic seamlessly translates these into quantitative values (Phillis and Andriantiatsaholiniaina, 2001). This gradation enables a more precise representation of sustainability's diverse dimensions, recognizing the inherent subjectivity in interpreting complex systems. Moreover, the adaptability of fuzzy logic enables dynamic adjustments in evaluation criteria, catering to the varying priorities and perspectives of evaluators.

Furthermore, fuzzy logic embodies an integrative approach, allowing the integration of expert knowledge to fortify the evaluation's robustness and effectiveness. This integration enables a holistic assessment aligned with the dynamic and diverse nature of agricultural systems

The Σ_i has been tested on new dataset featuring 1.8 million agronomic case scenarios, each representing unique farming practice combinations and pedoclimatic conditions. Each case scenario has been linked to its values of SOC changes (Δ SOC), N_2O emissions, NO_3-N leaching, and crop yield. Estimations for these trade-off components has derived from multiple sources, including the 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines, Green Water Footprint Accounting guidelines, Italian National Institute of Statistics, and international meta-analysis.

In addition to the balanced version of the Σ_i , where the four trade-off components have been aggregated with equal weight, this report introduces three further distinct series of the Σ_i . These series are a result of a tailored adjustment in the index aggregation rules, specifically designed to reflect varied perceptions of sustainability from three diverse stakeholder categories (a young farmers association, an agrochemical company, and a CAP paying agency)

2. Methods

2.1 Definition of the input data layer

The input layer consists of a dataset of agronomic case scenarios (CS), each representing a combination of pedo-climatic and management conditions. Table 1 lists the pedo-climatic and agronomic factors that have been considered in defining the CS dataset. We used data at Italian country level as a proof of concept, besides the same methodology can be applied to other spatial units and pedo-climatic conditions across Europe.

Table 1. Pedoclimatic and agronomic factors considered in the case-scenarios construction, with corresponding levels. The last four columns indicate whether a factor has been used to calculate a trade-off component.

Factor	Levels	Source	Δ SOC	N leaching	N ₂ O	Yield
Temperature regime	cool temperate, warm temperate	IPCC 2019 refinement	×		×	
Moisture regime	dry, moist	IPCC 2019, refinement	×		×	
Soil class	HAC, VOL, WET	IPCC 2019 refinement	×			
Soil texture	clay, silt, loam, sand	Franke et al. (2013)		×		
Soil tillage	full tillage, reduced tillage, no tillage	IPCC 2019 refinement	×	×	×	
Irrigation	none, drip, non-drip	IPCC 2019 and Daryanto et al. (2017)		×	×	×
OM input to soil	low, medium, high, high with manure	IPCC 2019 refinement	×			
Precipitation ranges (mm)	0-600, 600-1200, 1200-1800, >1800	Franke et al. (2013)		×	×	
N input (kg ha ⁻¹)	0, 50, 100, 150, 200	Hijbeek et al. (2017)		×	×	×
Type of organic N input	none, green manure, animal manure	Hijbeek et al. (2017)	×	×	×	×
Type of mineral N input	none, urea-based, nitrate-based, urea-nitrate balanced	Hijbeek et al. (2017)	×	×	×	×
Crops	barley, winter wheat, durum wheat, rye, oats, lentil, chickpea, soybean, field pea, grain pea, bean and green bean, potato, sorghum, maize, bare fallow, protein pea fallow, spring cereal fallow, winter cereal fallow	IPCC 2019 refinement, ISTAT (2023)			×	×
Crop residues	removed/burned, incorporated	IPCC 2019 refinement	×	×	×	

HAC, high activity clay soils; **VOL**, volcanic soils; **WET**, wetland or organic soils; **OM**, organic matter; **N**, nitrogen.

Factorial combinations of these factors generated nearly 1.8 million of agronomic case scenarios (CS), reflecting the plausible range of agricultural systems in Italy.

To better capture the interaction between soil carbon, nitrogen input, and subsequent greenhouse gas emissions—a crucial interplay not extensively covered in the IPCC methodology—we crafted four distinct management strategies based on the Organic Matter (OM) input classes outlined in the IPCC guidelines i.e., low, medium, high, and high with animal manure. Tailored N management strategies were devised for each OM class, incorporating various elements such as mineral and organic N fertilizers, nitrogen-fixing plants, crop residues, and rotational cover crops (Table 2). The crop-specific N fertilization levels ranged between the minimum and maximum amounts prescribed in national guidelines for integrated production (Rete Rurale Nazionale 2023). Notably, cover crops such as protein pea, spring grain mix, and winter grain mix were treated exclusively as cover crops, directing their complete biomass into soil incorporation without any harvest yield. Cover crops were neither associated with N fertilization nor irrigation, and no irrigation has been applied to cereals, out of maize and sorghum.

For each CS, the estimation of the four trade-off components (T-Ocs) - namely, Δ SOC, direct and indirect N₂O soil emissions, NO₃-N leaching, and crop yield—was performed utilizing equations and default emission factors from the 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (from here on referred as 2019

Refinement), and data sourced from various meta-analyses. For the detailed methodologies used to estimate Δ SOC, N_2O emissions, and NO_3-N leaching please refer to **Annex A**.

Crop selection for our study (Table 1) was based on coefficients available in the 2019 Refinement to estimate N content from residues. Statistical production data were obtained from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT), with yield ($Mg\ ha^{-1}$) calculated as the mean ratio of total production to cultivated areas from 2006 to 2022. To model the response curve of crop yield to N fertilization levels and types, a non-linear least squares mode has been applied, fitting data points from Hijbeeket al. (2017) meta-analysis. It has been assumed that the indicated N fertilization levels included mineral and organic components, with their ratio set as in Table 1. The effect of irrigation on yield has been quantified by considering a crop-specific yield percentage reduction derived from Daryanto et al. (2017).

Table 2. List of the IPCC classes of organic matter input and associated management practices.

IPCC OM input levels	Interpretation and description	N level ($kg\ ha^{-1}$)	Org frac (%)	Min Frac (%)	Min fert	Animal manure	Green manure	Residue burial	N fixing crops in rotation	Bare fallow in rotation	Vegetated fallow in rotation
Low	Conventional farming with no C input and N input solely from mineral sources.	0-200	0	100	Yes	No	No	NO	No	Yes	No
Medium	Sustainable farming with intermediate input from total mineral or organic sources or a 50:50 combination.	0-100	0	100	Yes	No/Yes*	No/Yes*	No/Yes*	Yes	No	Yes
			100	0							
			50	50							
High	Intensive agriculture reliant on mineral N fertilizers + green manure.	150-200	20	80	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
High + animal manure	Intensive agriculture reliant on mineral N fertilizers + animal manure.	150-200	80	20	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes

* Within the medium OM input category, organic input can alternately consist of crop residues or green manure or animal manure; in medium, high, and high + manure OM categories, mineral and organic fertilizers can be combined. **Org frac**, organic fraction; **Min frac**, mineral fraction; **Min fert**, mineral fertiliser; **N**, nitrogen

2.2. Analysis of the agronomic case scenarios through random forest and cluster analysis

The analyses have been conducted on a representative subset of the original dataset, consisting of 33,024 case scenarios, to reduce computational cost. All the analyses have been executed within the R Studio environment.

We applied Random Forest models to assess the impact of the considered management practices on each T-Oc. The RF model for crop yield excluded bare and vegetated fallows to ensure impartiality and unbiased results. We applied a k-fold cross-validation to ensure the results' reliability, splitting the subsample into five equally-sized folds (four for training, one for testing). The number of trees (ntree) has been optimized to 500 by trial and error, whereas the number of predictors at each split at each tree node (mtry) has been set as the square root of the total number of predictors (Hastie et al., 2009). The RF models' predictive accuracy has been evaluated using the root mean squared error (RMSE) (**Annex B**, Table 10-

B). Mean decrease of impurity (MDI) has been used to evaluate predictors' importance. MDI quantifies the importance of variables based on impurity reduction at decision tree nodes upon their utilization for partitioning. The obtained MDI values have been scaled between 0 and 1 to enhance comparison between the four trade-off components.

A hierarchical cluster (HC) analysis has been performed on the values of the four T-OCs to identify patterns of similarity in the input dataset. To analyze the composition of each extracted cluster, we examined the distribution of quantitative and qualitative variables within each cluster via v-test. A higher v-test value represents significant differences in cluster means compared to the overall mean, indicating the variable's relevance in discriminating the cluster. The direction of deviation from the global mean - positive or negative - indicate over- or under-representation of the specific variable within the cluster (**Annex B**, Tables 11-B to 14-B)

2.3. Fuzzy-logic aggregation

To rank the agronomic case scenarios, we designed a composite index, the \sum ommit index, that employs fuzzy logic to combine the four trade-off components (input variables). This method was chosen to accommodate the notion of partial truth and involved four primary stages: fuzzification, inference, defuzzification, and \sum I categorization.

Fuzzification: This initial step involved converting the input variables (the 4 T-Ocs) into fuzzy membership values using specific membership functions. These functions, defined across the input variables' space, describe the degree to which an input belongs to each fuzzy set. Three fuzzy sets have been established within this process: 'low,' 'medium,' and 'high.' Sigmoidal functions were applied to 'low' and 'high' sets, while a Gaussian function was used for the 'medium' set (Figure 1A). Five membership functions have been assigned to the \sum i (very low, low, medium, high, and very high) to better discriminate the trade-off assessment across case scenarios (Annex B, table 15-B). Before fuzzification, the input variables have been standardized within a range of 0 to 1. The fuzzification operation involved determining membership values for each input variable (T-Oc) within its respective fuzzy set. This determination was achieved by projecting the input value from the x-axis onto the membership functions along the y-axis. (Figure 1a).

Inference: The system's reasoning process relied on if-then rules establishing the relationships among the four T-Ocs and the \sum i. These rules encompassed all potential combinations of input sets, employing 'and' logical operators, resulting in 81 rules. For instance, a rule might state, "if Δ SOC is 'high' and N_2O is 'high' and NO_3-N is 'high' and Yield is 'low', then the \sum i is low" (e.g., Figure 1b). In the if-then rules, the combination of the fuzzy sets relative to the inputs (e.g., Δ SOC is 'high' and N_2O is 'high' and NO_3-N is 'high' and Yield is 'low') constitute the antecedent, while the fuzzy set relative to the output constitutes the consequent (e.g., \sum i is 'low'). The consequent has been established for each rule by assigning a representative numerical value to each fuzzy set corresponding to the inputs, i.e., low = 0.15, medium = 0.5, and high = 0.75.

These values have been used to calculate a weighted average (μ) of the four T-Ocs, according to Eq. (1):

$$\mu = \frac{((1 - \Delta SOC_m) * \Delta SOC_w) + ((1 - N_2O_m) * N_2O_w) + ((1 - NO_3-N_m) * NO_3-N_w) + (Y_m * Y_w)}{\Delta SOC_w + N_2O_w + NO_3-N_w + Y_w} \quad (1)$$

where the subscript m indicates the representative numerical values of the fuzzy set attributed to each T-Oc in a specific rule, and the subscript w indicates its relative weight.

In our first iteration of the method, each T-Oc was equally weighted. Differentiated weights have been used thereafter (see section 2.5) to obtain alternative rule sets based on stakeholder narratives.

As an example, given the rule "if Δ SOC is 'high' and N_2O is 'medium' and NO_3-N is 'high' and Yield is 'low', then the $\sum i$ is 'low'" and assuming a balanced weight distribution (each T-Oc has a weight of 25), the weighted average (μ) would be computed as follows (Eq. (2)):

$$\mu = \frac{((1 - 0.85) * 25) + ((1 - 0.5) * 25) + ((1 - 0.85) * 25) + (0.15 * 25)}{100} \quad (2)$$

The consequent (i.e., $\sum i$, from very low to very high) has been then computed as in Table 3.

Table 3. Thresholds for determining the fuzzy set to assign to the consequent ($\sum i$) based on the weighted average (μ) of the antecedents (trade-off components)

$\mu \leq 0.2$	$\sum i$ is 'very low'
$0.2 < \mu \leq 0.4$	$\sum i$ is 'low'
$0.4 < \mu \leq 0.6$	$\sum i$ is 'medium'
$0.6 < \mu \leq 0.8$	$\sum i$ is 'high'
$\mu > 0.8$	$\sum i$ is 'very high'

The Mamdani minimum inference method has been applied to determine the membership value of the output variable ($\sum i$). The method applies the "min" operator to derive the fuzzy output set by taking the minimum value among the antecedent fuzzy sets, subsequently using this minimum value to clip the output fuzzy set defined in the consequent rule (Figure 2B).

Defuzzification: this process involved deriving an exact measure from the aggregated membership values using the centroid method. This method calculates the centre of gravity within the aggregated fuzzy set output area, resulting in a single exact value, the $\sum i$, ranging from 0 (bad) to 1 (good) (figure 2C).

$\sum i$ categorization: the $\sum i$ values have been categorized using Jenks natural breaks classification to ease interpretation. This method divides the data into groups by optimizing within-group variance and maximizing between-group variance. Four natural breakpoints emerged, leading to five categories in the values of $\sum i$: 'poor' ($\sum i < 0.43$), 'below-average' ($0.43 < \sum i < 0.54$), 'average' ($0.54 < \sum i < 0.62$), 'above average' ($0.62 < \sum i < 0.69$), and 'elevated' ($\sum i > 0.69$).

is summarized in Table 4, where the symbol \approx indicates that the mean of the distribution of the weights assigned by the expert is approximately 25, the symbol \downarrow indicates that the mean is below 25 and the symbol \uparrow that it is above

Table 4. trend of the mean weights assigned to the four T-Ocs by expert across narratives NT1 - Young farmers, NT2 - Agrochem corporation, and NT3 - CAP paying agency, compared to the balanced narrative (NT0), where T-Ocs were weighted 25 each.

	Δ SOC	N ₂ O emissions	NO ₃ -N leaching	Crop yield
NT1:	\approx	\downarrow	\downarrow	\uparrow
NT2:	\downarrow	\downarrow	\approx	\uparrow
NT3:	\uparrow	\approx	\approx	\downarrow

The same Jenks breaks classification scheme illustrated in paragraph 2.4 has been applied to the \sum_i series obtained in each narrative, leading to five \sum_i classes per narrative: poor, below-average, average, above-average, and elevated. A v-test was then applied to characterize the "elevated" \sum_i classes within each scenario based on the most influential management practices

2.5. Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) and dashboard generation

To promote the dissemination of the agronomic scenario dataset, it has been made freely downloadable from an online repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10014452>).

Additionally, to enable easy querying of the dataset and exploration of the scenario cases along with associated values of trade-off components and the \sum_{commit} index, a web-based dashboard has been developed (<https://github.com/kofm/sommit-dashboard>).

Within this intuitive dashboard interface, the case- scenarios are represented as points in a 3D space. Their positioning and distance derive from a multivariate statistical analysis, the Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA). MFA has been specifically chosen for its ability to synthesize and visually interpret complex and extensive datasets.

MFA permits simultaneous analysis of diverse data types, including categorical and numerical variables. Its significance lies in conducting a holistic analysis, crucial within our context where these data groups cover various aspects of agronomic case scenarios, spanning environmental conditions, management practices, crop and trade-off components.

Prior the analysis, each group of variables has been normalized to prevent any single group from dominating the analysis due to its size or variability, ensuring an equitable representation of all facets.

The outcomes of the MFA are displayed as a plot where each point corresponds to a unique agronomic case-scenario. A greater distance between points indicates higher variability or difference in the considered agronomic case-scenario and their associated variables. Points are color-coded based on their rating provided by the \sum_{commit} index, allowing for quick comparative analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Effect of pedoclimatic conditions and management practices on the trade-off components and the \sum_{commit} index

All pedo-climatic and management practices impacted the four T-Ocs, albeit with varying importance according to the RF models (Figure 3). Here, we discuss the most relevant factors in modulating each T-Oc.

Δ SOC (Figure 3A): Soil organic carbon changes were primarily influenced by OM input - specifically, its level and type (animal/green manure)—followed by precipitation, crop residue incorporation, and soil class. Soil tillage intensity, N fertilization level, and crop type had lower importance in shaping Δ SOC.

N₂O emissions (Figure 3B): Precipitation levels and OM input were the main drivers, alongside N fertilization levels and the type of mineral fertilizer. These factors also emerged as the most influential on *NO₃-N leaching (Figure 3C)*, suggesting a strong correlation between these two T-Ocs. Soil texture, management, and crop choice had minor effects on these outcomes.

Crop yield (Figure 3D): N fertilization level and the type of mineral fertilizer were the top-ranking factors, followed by crop type, irrigation level, and type of organic fertilization.

Figure 2: Results of the feature importance analysis from the Random Forest model using farmers' management and pedoclimatic factors as predictors of **A)** Δ SOC, **B)** N₂O emissions, **C)** NO₃-N leaching, and **D)** crop yield in the agronomical dataset. The x-axis presents their relative importance in terms of Mean Decrease in Impurity. OM, organic matter; N, nitrogen. The length of the horizontal bars is proportional to the importance of each factor, with longer bars indicating higher importance than other factors.

Cluster 1: This cluster showed a balanced distribution of Δ SOC values, encompassing both positive and negative values, indicating a combination of CS associated with CO₂ emissions and removal. Additionally, it shows reduced N₂O emissions compared to the global average, with mean NO₃-N leaching at approximately half of the global average. The scaled mean yield within this cluster is roughly half of the global scaled yield. It primarily comprises scenarios featuring vegetated and bare fallows, minimal N fertilization, crop residue burial, absence of irrigation, and annual precipitation below 600 mm. The components of this cluster were predominantly categorized within the Σ ommit index classes "below average" and "average" (figure 3E).

Cluster 2: This cluster displays a higher proportion of negative Δ SOC values, suggesting increased CO₂ removal compared to Cluster 1. It also exhibits reduced N₂O emissions compared to the global average, with slightly higher mean NO₃-N leaching. Moreover, the scaled mean yield surpasses the global scaled mean. Cluster 2 is characterized by occurrences of annual precipitation in the range of 600-1200 mm, non-drip irrigation, intermediate N fertilization, and a prevalence of specific crops like winter and spring cereals, soybean, and potato. The components of this cluster were predominantly categorized within Σ i classes "above average" and "elevated" (figure 3E).

Cluster 3: This cluster presents positive Δ SOC values, indicating greater CO₂ emissions compared to Cluster 1. It showcases increased N₂O emissions and NO₃-N fluxes relative to other clusters, with a substantially higher scaled mean yield compared to the global average. This cluster is dominated by a humid climate, limited organic matter input, removal of crop residues, intensive tillage, and high mineral N fertilization. It primarily features summer crops such as sorghum and potato. The individuals within this cluster predominantly belong to the Σ i classes "poor", "below average", and "average" (figure 3E).

Figure 3: Violin boxplots representing the data distribution within the extracted clusters of **A)** Δ SOC, **B)** N₂O emissions, **C)** NO₃-N leaching, and **D)** scaled crop yield values. Different colours indicate distinct clusters (cluster 1 - purple, cluster 2 - green, cluster 3 - yellow). The red dashed lines indicate the overall mean of each trade-off component. **E)** Distribution of Σ ommit index (Σ i) values from the balanced narrative (NT0) across the five Σ i classes (poor, below-average, average, above-average, elevated). The bars depict the distribution of the values of each class within clusters.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis of the Σ ommit index according to stakeholders' priorities

Figure 4 illustrates the medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) of the Σ I values across the levels of the main management practices in the three narratives.

NT1: under NT1, Σ_i values showed larger and left-skewed distribution compared to NT0 (balanced scenario). Management practices leading to decreased yield, such as low N input, absence of irrigation, and fallows, resulted in lower Σ_i distribution medians than NT0. Conversely, higher N input levels and manure application depicted higher Σ_i distribution medians due to increased yields.

NT2: this scenario showed Σ_i values with trends that were intermediate between NT1 and NT3. However, the distribution here was more inclined towards lower Σ_i values.

NT3: under NT3, the Σ_i values displayed a narrower and right-skewed distribution in comparison to NT0, suggesting an overall increase in Σ_i within this narrative. Practices linked to reduced yield, like bare and vegetated fallows, low N input, and rainfed crops, yielded higher Σ_i medians compared to NT0. Conversely, lower OM input and higher N levels resulted in lower Σ_i values when compared to NT0.

Figure 4: median and interquartile (IQ) ranges of the Σ ommit index (Σ_i) values for each level of the main management practices under narratives 1 (NT1 – young farmers), 2 (NT2 - agrochem corporation), and 3 (NT3 - CAP paying agency). Black empty rhombus and dashed lines represent the median and IQ ranges of the Σ_i values under NT0 - balanced narrative. Red points below the black rhombus indicate lower Σ_i median compared to NT0. Green points above indicate higher Σ_i median than NT0. OM, organic matter; N, nitrogen. Vegetated fallow – spring cereal fallow, winter cereal fallow, protein pea fallow; Winter cereals - winter wheat, durum wheat, barley, oats, and rye; Beans and pulses - field pea, grain pea, soybean, chickpea, lentil, bean and green bean.

The heatmap depicted in Figure 5 showcases v-values associated with primary management practices within the 'elevated' Σi class. Positive values (shown in green) indicate overrepresented practices, while negative values (illustrated in red) indicate underrepresentation. White areas denote practices that do not significantly characterize the elevated Σi class. Notable characteristics of the 'elevated' Σi class include: High organic matter (OM) input combined with animal manure across all narratives.

- Nitrogen (N) inputs of 150 kg ha⁻¹ in NT1 and NT2, and 50 kg ha⁻¹ in NT0 and NT1.
- Predominance of animal manure as the primary N source across all narratives, followed by mineral N sources, without differentiation among the different types. The absence of N input consistently showed underrepresentation in all narratives.
- Prevalence of non-drip irrigation in NT1 and NT2, followed by drip irrigation, with lower and equal representation across all narratives. The absence of irrigation consistently appeared underrepresented in all narratives.
- No-soil tillage, with both fallow categories consistently underrepresented in all narratives.
- Dominance of winter and durum wheat, barley, oat, and rye as the most represented crops. Both fallow categories consistently showed underrepresentation in all narratives.
- Crop residue removal.

Figure 5: Heatmap illustrating the v-values of the level of the main management practices within the 'elevated' Σi class across narratives NT0 (balanced), NT1 (young farmers), NT2 (Agrochem corporation), and NT3 (CAP paying agency). Red denotes underrepresented levels (negative v-values). Green indicates overrepresented levels (positive v-values). Colour intensity reflects the degree of a level representation. White areas indicate practices not represented in the 'elevated' Σi class. OM, organic matter; N, nitrogen. Vegetated fallow – spring cereal fallow, winter cereal fallow, protein pea fallow; Winter cereals - winter wheat, durum wheat, barley, oats, and rye; Beans and pulses - field pea, grain pea, soybean, chickpea, lentil, bean and green bean.

3.3. Online dashboard

The Σ ommit Trade-offs analysis dashboard is a web-based user interface designed to explore the case-scenario dataset alongside related trade-off components and Σ ommit index values.

This dashboard introduces a 3D scatterplot visualization that encapsulates three key aspects of agronomic case scenarios: Environment (E), Management (M), and Trade-off components (T). This visualization showcases what we call EMT distances, synthesizing these three dimensions into an easy-to-interpret representation.

Navigating the interactive 3D plot within the dashboard is intuitive. Users can employ a series of filters to tailor the displayed data according to specific criteria, focusing on the most pertinent agronomic case scenarios. The filters also include the narratives due to their relevance in shaping the calculation of Σ ommit index values.

Interacting with the 3D plot is user-friendly—hovering the mouse over any point triggers a popup window displaying a detailed breakdown of the agronomic case scenario and its associated index. Users can rotate the plot, view it from different angles, zoom in for a closer examination, or zoom out for a broader perspective. Additionally, an option to capture a screenshot allows for future reference or sharing with others.

This visualization serves as a tool for visually comparing the considered cases based on calculated EMT distances. Viewers can assess the similarity between cases by observing their relative positions and colours. Points' proximity indicates similarity, with greater distances suggesting higher dissimilarities. The colour-coded scheme acts as a quick reference for Σ ommit index ratings—dark purples denote lower values, while light yellows indicate higher values.

This visualization aids non-experts by providing a simplified visual representation of the relative variability in Environment, Management, and Trade-off components among the considered agronomic case scenarios.

4. Discussion

4.1. Strengths and weaknesses of the proposed methodology

The work undertaken in WP5 yielded two primary outcomes. Firstly, a dataset comprising approximately two million agronomic case-scenarios emerged. Each scenario embodies a unique combination of management practices and pedoclimatic conditions, linked to reference values for Δ SOC, N₂O emissions, NO₃-N leaching, crop yield, and uncertainty estimates. This dataset has been made available to the scientific community through an online repository accompanied by an interactive dashboard facilitating data exploration and queries.

This dataset has been obtained by integrating equations and emission factors from established IPCC Tier 1 guidelines with knowledge from existing meta-analyses. This approach, although generic, allowed us to account for a wide spectrum of pedo-climatic conditions and agronomic practices, providing a practical and reliable alternative to time-consuming field measurements and complex agro-ecosystem simulation models.

A notable advancement in our methodology compared to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines and their 2019 Refinement involves the concerted effort to correlate precise N fertilization strategies with IPCC OM input levels. This endeavour aimed to capture the interplay between N to C input levels, an aspect not extensively covered in the IPCC guidelines. Furthermore, our refinement of the IPCC methodology for estimating NO₃-N leaching explicitly considered various factors, including soil textures, tillage, drainage conditions, precipitation levels, nitrogen uptake, fixation, and residue management. This refinement draws upon information from the Gray Water Footprint (GWF) accounting guidelines.

The second outcome is the Σ OMMIT index, a metric designed to evaluate trade-offs between four components resulting from agricultural activities, including tillage, irrigation, N fertilization, OM input, crop choice, and residue management. The formalization of a single index quantifying the agronomic performance contributed to streamlining the evaluation

process while simplifying interpretation for a wide range of stakeholders, thereby enhancing its potential applicability across various real-world use cases. Explicit limitations of our trade-off analysis are the lack of consideration of i) the economic component, which could align more closely with the practical demands of stakeholders to balance immediate gains and long-term sustainability (e.g., Liu et al., 2022; Samarawickrema and Belcher, 2008.; Shirsath and Aggarwal, 2021), and ii) CH₄ emissions, which mostly characterize rice cultivation. However, the flexibility of the \sum_i fuzzy-logic framework allows for extension to other components and the fine-tuning using expert opinion to consider other sustainability priorities (Cavallaro, 2015). Another challenging point is the assignment of C and N emissions/losses to a single cropping season, which could raise criticism due to the interconnection of cropping systems and associated emissions. The \sum_i can be computed for each crop in a sequence, extending the boundary of the trade-off analysis and offering a means to evaluate the crop rotations.

Overall, the proposed assessment system, consisting of the dataset, the Σ OMMIT index, and a user-friendly dashboard, can provide a useful complement to the current IPCC methodology for national GHG inventories and can be utilized by EU countries to evaluate agricultural impact on global warming.

4.2. Trends in trade-off components

The analysis of the input dataset revealed that the level of OM and N input, the type of N source (mineral or organic), the irrigation type, and the crop choice are the primary management practices affecting the T-Ocs. Low OM input and exclusive reliance on mineral fertilization yielded the highest CO₂ emissions values from soil C depletion. On the contrary, increased N fertilization levels and substitution of mineral fertilization with animal manure increased CO₂ removal from the atmosphere to the soil, in line with findings from Xia et al. (2017), Xu et al. (2021), and Zhou et al. (2017). According to IPCC methodology, once the reference SOC stock value is established as a function of the climate and soil type, it must be adjusted using stock change factors accounting for the impacts of land use (F_{LU}), soil management (F_{MG}), and input levels (F_I). In our study, we have estimated the annual changes in SOC stocks arising from the transition from an initial state to a final stable state of soil tillage and input levels. Notably, when transitioning to a high OM level with the addition of manure, the F_I factor employed to modify the reference SOC stock value reaches its maximum value. This occurrence clarifies the observed reduction in net CO₂ emissions associated with high input levels and the replacement of mineral fertilization with organic sources.

Our trade-off analysis revealed a gradual increase in N losses with increased N input, regardless of the N source (mineral, green manure, or animal manure). Indeed, the partial substitution of mineral inputs with organic fertilizers did not lead to significant changes in N flows, suggesting that the level of N input exerts a greater influence than its form. This trend finds partial support in the conclusion drawn by Shcherbak et al. (2014), Han et al. (2017), Xia et al. (2017) and Zhang et al. (2020). In IPCC Tier 1 equation for calculating direct N₂O emissions, the quantity of N inputs added to the soil is multiplied by an emission factor (EF1) stratified by climate (dry/wet). Only in wet climates, EF1 is further stratified by fertilizer source (mineral/organic). The lack of finer disaggregation, especially in dry climates and for organic N sources, may partially account for the greater impact resulting from the N input quantity rather than its form. For indirect N₂O emissions from N volatilization, the quantity of soil N inputs is first multiplied by a volatilization fraction, which is stratified by source (mineral/organic) and, only for mineral fertilizer, by type. Then, it is multiplied by a volatilization emission factor (EF4), which is stratified by climate (dry/wet). For indirect N₂O emissions from N leaching, a single leaching fraction for wet climates (zero for dry climates) and a single emission fraction (EF5), devoid of climate differentiation, are provided. Despite efforts to refine the IPCC leaching fraction with the more detailed GWF accounting

guidelines, we did not find precise information regarding the effects of the different mineral/organic N types. Once again, this may explain why the overall N input quantity resulted in a stronger impact on N fluxes than its form.

A positive connection between crop yields and increased levels of N and OM input emerged from our trade-off analysis, although crop yield ceased to increase beyond 150 kg ha⁻¹. According to Hijbeek et al. (2017) meta-analysis, from which the yield response curves to different types and levels of N fertilization have been extracted, organic inputs can benefit crop yield by improving soil water retention in dry climates and reducing soil compaction in wet areas. However, they suggested that root or tuber crops might benefit more than cereals from increased soil OM, as their successful cultivation and harvesting depend more on the soil structure.

Irrigation had minimal impact on ΔSOC and N₂O fluxes but slightly increased NO₃-N leaching under non-drip irrigation. Previous research has highlighted significant effects of irrigation on soil carbon sequestration and N₂O emission factors (Denef et al., 2008; Yan et al., 2022, Emde et al. 2021, Cayuela et al., 2017). The discrepancy with our results may be due to the neglect of the irrigation effects in the 2019 Refinement to estimate SOC stocks changes. As well, while accounting for pedoclimatic conditions and N input, the IPCC method lacks comprehensive consideration of irrigation impact on N₂O direct emissions, except for its inclusion in estimating indirect N₂O emissions from N leaching, where however a finer distinction among different irrigation methods is lacking.

We were unable to refine the yield response to different irrigation types due to the absence of available meta-analysis considering the effects of various irrigation methods on the considered crops. Consequently, our trade-off analysis solely focused on the presence or absence of irrigation, resulting in equal yield assigned to drip and non-drip irrigation, which have been differentiated only for N-leaching calculation purposes.

Regarding crop management, vegetated fallow, where 100% of the crop biomass is incorporated into the soil, resulted in soil C enrichment, and reduced N₂O emissions and NO₃-N leaching compared to bare fallow, indicating a higher CO₂ removal from the atmosphere and reduced N fluxes, in line with Quemada et al. (2013), Tonitto et al. (2006), and Nouri et al. (2022). Indeed, in the GWF accounting methodology used to refine the IPCC leaching fraction, returning crop residues to soils is considered a practice reducing N leaching as it helps to maintain soil OM and hold nutrients in the soil. Our analysis indicated that cultivating legumes slightly increased NO₃-N leaching, in line with Tripolskaja et al. (2023) and Nouri et al. (2022) findings. Notably, when applying the IPCC default coefficients for estimating N additions from crop residues, beans and peas, followed by potatoes, exhibited the higher N fraction in both their above-ground and below-ground residues, explaining why their cultivation has been associated with higher NO₃-N leaching.

However, when delving into the implications of our trade-off analysis, it is important to highlight that our primary aim was to create a methodology to use when context-specific data are unavailable, and when a reference dataset is lacking. Our findings are based on a set of assumptions and simplifications based on official guidelines and meta-analysis and are specific to Italy's climatic zones. These results may differ when the method is applied to other spatial and temporal contexts. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the same methodology can be replicated using data from alternative and more precise data sources, such as field experiments and simulation models.

4.3. *Σommit index behaviour under alternative narratives*

In the balanced weighting scheme, the most favourable Σi were associated with CSs characterized by intermediate N input levels (50-150 kg ha⁻¹), elevated OM input, cultivation of winter cereals, and implementation of irrigation for non-winter cereal crops. As discussed earlier, increasing OM input increased soil C stock without elevating the N₂O emissions, which were more elicited by N fertilizer quantity rather than its form (mineral or organic). Moreover, yield increased along with N input, plateauing at 150 kg N ha⁻¹, indicating that further fertilizations heightened N losses without

significantly enhancing yield. Notably, irrigation significantly bolstered yield, which plummeted in its absence, though its impact on the other three T-Ocs resulted negligible, except for an increased N-NO₃- leaching under non-drip irrigation. The \sum_i adaptability to user-perceived priorities and its sensitivity were tested by changing the weighting scheme based on expert opinion. Transitioning to NT1 (young farmers) narrowed the range of \sum_i values due to the increased importance assigned to crop yield as compared to the other two narratives. Notably, crop yield is the sole factor expected to positively contribute to the \sum_i index. Consequently, even a slight yield reduction in NT1 had a more pronounced impact due to the heightened sensitivity of the \sum_i .

In contrast to NT1, NT3 (the CAP paying agency) displayed a significant weight redistribution towards Δ SOC, with relatively less importance assigned by experts to crop yield. Almost all case scenarios within this narrative achieved higher \sum_i values, suggesting a less stringent evaluation. Under this narrative, the practices contributing to increased SOC stocks, like OM input and the incorporation of both green and animal manures, resulted in elevated \sum_i values. Concurrently, management practices linked with low yields, such as lower N input levels and bare and vegetated fallow, were less penalized than NT1, gaining higher \sum_i values.

The final analysis on the 'elevated' \sum_i class provided an overall summary of the management practices characterizing the best CSs under all four narratives. Except for N input, which markedly differed across narratives, the best CSs were consistently characterized by high OM input, specifically animal manure, no soil tillage, and cultivation of winter cereals, with the implementation of irrigation for the other crop categories. The absence of fertilization was consistently under-represented while the crop residue incorporation did not emerge as a prominent practice within the best CS in any narrative. In the 2019 Refinement, the influence of crop residue on Δ SOC has been generally incorporated into the OM input categories without explicit consideration through a dedicated SOC stock change factor. Indeed, crop residue biomass has a short biogenic cycle due to the fast decomposition and its impact on CO₂ emission/removal is considered neutral in the short time. In contrast, the IPCC methodology has crop-specific coefficients for estimating both above-ground and below-ground residue fractions and their N content to account for the impact of crop residues on N₂O emissions. This difference in accounting methods may justify why, in our analysis, the incorporation of residues has not emerged as a prominent practice associated with elevated \sum_i values.

However, it must be acknowledged that variations in the weighting scheme led to fluctuations in the boundaries and distribution of the \sum_i values, but optimal CSs were almost stable across narratives, except for the marked variation in N input level. This consistency can be partially attributed to fuzzy logic's capability to incorporate subjectivity and manage uncertainty. Fuzzy logic indeed enabled capturing overall trends in data behaviour, accommodating variations in component weights without inducing significant deviations in the final index.

5. Conclusions

The evaluation of the complex interplay among alternative farmers' management practices, cropping system productivity and environmental impacts is imperative to reduce climate change impact of agriculture, and needs to be sustained by reliable facts and quantitative data. As an alternative to costly field measurements and complex simulation models, this study proposes a methodology combining well-established guidelines, meta-analyses, and fuzzy logic to build a metric intended to transparently assess trade-offs and facilitate stakeholders' decision-making. The evaluation framework relies on an open-access dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10014452>), accessible to the community via a user-friendly graphical interface (<https://github.com/kofm/sommit-dashboard>). Despite being limited in the number of trade-off components considered, the structure of the \sum_{ommit} index facilitates the seamless integration of other components

connected to agricultural sustainability, while being flexible to diverse analytical needs and stakeholder preferences, extending its utility at National/European level for policy makers to support targeted policies measures.

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Annex A: methodology for the estimation of trade-off components of SOMMIT index based on refinement 2019 of IPCC guidelines 2006 for national GHG inventories

1. Introduction

The objective of this Annex A is to present methodologies and equations used for the estimation of the four SOMMIT trade-off components, which were retrieved mainly from IPCC guidelines for National GHG Inventories (IPCC 2006, IPCC, 2019): change in soil carbon stock, nitrous oxide emissions, nitrate leaching and crop yield.

Sources and methodologies for the definition of parameters and emission factors provided by refinement 2019 of IPCC guidelines are briefly described, highlighting improvements introduced with respect to IPCC guidelines 2006.

The updated values of variables and emission factors from Refinement 2019 have been used in our Italian case study, where available:

- The reference C stock depending on climate region and soil type.
- C stock change factors relative to land use, tillage regime and C input
- Emission factors for the direct N₂O emissions (kg N₂O-N/kg N fertilizer added to soil) differentiated per dry and wet climates and per form of fertilizer (synthetic/other)
- Fraction of N contained in fertilizers which volatilize (differentiated per organic and synthetic fertilizers) and which is subject to leaching/runoff
- Emission factors for indirect N₂O emissions from N volatilization (differentiated per dry and wet climates) and from N leaching and runoff (kg N₂O-N/kg N volatilized or leached/run-off)
- Factor for mineralized N resulting from loss of soil organic C stocks in mineral soils through land-use change or management practices (F_{SOM}).

In national GHG inventories (GHGI), annually submitted under UNFCCC, direct and indirect N₂O emissions from N inputs of synthetic and organic fertilizer to managed agricultural soils are reported in the agriculture sector, while emissions resulting from soil C changes are reported in LULUCF sector; F_{SOM} is the only one element of IPCC methodology referring to the trade-offs between soil C change and other GHG emissions from soils: it accounts for N₂O emissions from N mineralization associated with C loss, but does not represent a slower nitrogen mineralization rate when there is soil carbon enhancement. Exception made for F_{SOM} , carbon input to soil and nitrogen input to soil are accounted for separately in national GHG inventories estimated after IPCC Tier 1 methodology.

N₂O emissions estimated after IPCC guidelines are not sensitive to different management practices (tillage regime, organic matter input level, irrigation regime) and to soil carbon saturation level. Thus, in task 5.2 and 5.3 of SOMMIT project an effort was made to enhance the interrelationships among soil C and N input and subsequent GHG emissions, by associating a specific N input (levels and type, mineral, organic, or both) to each IPCC organic matter input class, as described in paragraph 2.1 of this report.

2. SOC stock change

The IPCC Tier 1 guidelines provide reference values of C stock for mineral soils (i.e., containing an organic C pool influenced by land-use and management activities) stratified by climatic zone and soil class.

According to the IPCC Tier 1 guidelines (equation 2.25, Volume 4), evaluating changes in soil C stocks in the upper 30 cm necessitates focusing on variations in land use, soil management, and organic matter input. According to the same source, a steady-state SOC stock can be reached in a period of 20 years after activity changes, as a default.

Compared to a starting condition, the methodology involves assessing the changes in organic C stock after management alterations. Our study focused on long-term cultivated lands (cropland remaining cropland land use sub-category), including regions where annual crops have been cultivated for over two decades. All possible changes in soil management (i.e., no tillage, reduced tillage, and full tillage) and OM input (low, medium, high, high with manure) contributed to estimate the annual rate of soil carbon gain or loss (Tables 2-A, 3-A, 4-A).

The inherent assumptions include attaining a stable, spatially averaged organic C stock after 20 years with linear changes toward a new equilibrium. Annual C stock changes (ΔSOC , Mg yr⁻¹) were converted to Mg of CO₂ emissions/removals, multiplying the values by 44/12 (ratio of molecular weights): negative values of ΔSOC (soil carbon depletion) are expressed as positive CO₂ emissions from the soil to the atmosphere and positive values of ΔSOC (soil carbon enrichment) as CO₂ removals from the atmosphere to the soil (negative sign of CO₂ emissions).

Here below is reported the equation for the estimation of annual change in organic stocks in mineral soils. Source: Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2006):

EQUATION 2.25
ANNUAL CHANGE IN ORGANIC CARBON STOCKS IN MINERAL SOILS

$$\Delta C_{Mineral} = \frac{(SOC_0 - SOC_{(0-T)})}{D}$$

$$SOC_{Mineral} = \sum_{c,s,i} (SOC_{REF_{c,s,i}} \cdot F_{LU_{c,s,i}} \cdot F_{MG_{c,s,i}} \cdot F_{I_{c,s,i}} \cdot A_{c,s,i})$$

(Note: T is used in place of D in the $\Delta C_{Mineral}$ equation if T is ≥ 20 years, see note below associated with the parameter D)

Where c represents the climate zones, s the soil types, and i the set of management systems that are present in a country.

D=T= 20 years; A_{c,s,i}= land area of the stratum being estimated [ha]

SOC_{REF} is the default reference condition of soil organic carbon stocks (with native vegetation) for mineral soils (tonnes C ha⁻¹ in 0-30 cm depth); table 2.3 of Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines provide the reference values for the combination of six soil classes and nine climate zone. In Table 1-A here below, the Tier 1 values of SOC_{REF} for soil classes and climate zone of the examined Italian case study are reported.

Table 1-A. Default reference (under native vegetation) soil organic C stocks (SOC_{ref}) for mineral soils (tonnes c ha⁻¹ in 0-30 cm depth) for the Italian climate zone and soil classes

temp_regime	moist_regime	soil_class	Refinement 2019		IPCC 2006
			SOC _{REF}	uncertainty	SOC _{REF}
Cool	Dry	HAC	43	±8%	50
Cool	Dry	LAC	33	±90%	33
Cool	Dry	SAN	13	±33%	34

Cool	Dry	VOL	20	±90%	20
Cool	Dry	WET	87	±90%	87
Cool	Moist	HAC	81	±5%	95
Cool	Moist	LAC	76	±51%	85
Cool	Moist	SAN	51	±13%	71
Cool	Moist	POD	128	±14%	115
Cool	Moist	VOL	136	±14%	130
Cool	Moist	WET	128	±13%	87
Warm	Dry	HAC	24	±5%	38
Warm	Dry	LAC	19	±16	24
Warm	Dry	SAN	10	±5%	19
Warm	Dry	VOL	84	±65%	70
Warm	Dry	WET	74	±17%	88
Warm	Moist	HAC	64	±5%	88
Warm	Moist	LAC	55	±8%	63
Warm	Moist	SAN	36	±23%	34
Warm	Moist	POD	143	±30%	NA
Warm	Moist	VOL	138	±12%	80
Warm	Moist	WET	135	±28%	88

Values of IPCC 2006 are presented as mean stocks with a nominal error estimate of ±90% (expressed as 2x standard deviations as percent of the mean) assumed for all soil-climate types. Data were derived mainly from soil databases described in the following papers:

- *Jobbagy, E.G. and Jackson, R.B. (2000). The vertical distribution of soil organic carbon and its relation to climate and vegetation. Ecological Applications 19(2): 423-436.*
- *Bernoux, M., Carvalho, M.D.S., Volkoff, B. and Cerri, C.C. (2002). Brazil's soil carbon stocks. Soil Science Society of America Journal 66:888-896.*

Values of Refinement 2019 are presented in the format of the mean for the soil by climate combination ± the 95% confidence limit expressed as a percentage of the mean (that is ± 1.96 * standard error /mean *100). Data are derived mainly from two main sources unless otherwise noted:

- *Batjes, N. (2010) A global framework of soil organic carbon stocks under native vegetation for use with the simple assessment option of the Carbon Benefits Project system. In: p. 79. Wageningen, The Netherlands: ISRIC World Soil Information.*
- *Batjes, N. (2011) Soil organic carbon stocks under native vegetation - Revised estimates for use with the simple assessment option of the Carbon Benefits Project system. Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment 142: 365-373.*

Climate classes are defined using elevation, mean annual temperature, mean annual precipitation, mean annual precipitation to potential evapotranspiration ratio and frost occurrence, while soil classes are inferred from the FAO-1990/WRB-2006 classification, as described in chapter 1 of Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines 2006 (Annex 3A.5).

Based on the climate and soil maps of Carre et al. (2010) and Batjes (2010), respectively, Italy can be categorized into five climate types (polar moist; cool temperate dry; cool temperate moist; warm temperate dry; warm temperate moist) and four soil types (high activity clay, sand, volcanic, wetland or organic) (Figures A1). We retained all categories except

the polar moist climate and sand soil, which are negligibly represented in Italian agricultural areas (EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2018).

The predominant soil class is soils with high activity clay (HAC) minerals, which are lightly to moderately weathered soils dominated by 2:1 silicate clay minerals (in the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB) classification: Leptosols, Vertisols, Kastanozems, Chernozems, Phaeozems, Luvisols, Alisols, Albeluvisols, Solonetz, Calcisols, Gypsisols, Umbrisols, Cambisols, Regosols).

Figure 1-A. IPCC maps of A) climatic zones (Carre et al., 2010) and B) soil types (Batjes 2010) elaborated by JRC within ESDAC as thematic Data Layers.

Assuming no land use change and considering only long-term cultivated land use (cropland), the following stock change factors have been considered for Italy:

Table 2-A. Relative stock change factors (over 20 years) for land use (F_{LU}) in climatic and soil conditions of Italy (from table 5.5 of Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines)

LAND USE	temp_regime	moist_regime	Refinement 2019		IPCC 2006	
			F_{LU}	error	F_{LU}	error
LongTermCultivated	Boreal	Moist	0.70	±12%	0.8	±9%
		Dry	0.77	±14%	0.69	±12%
	Cool	Dry	0.77	±14%	NA	NA
		Moist	0.70	±12%	NA	NA
	Warm	Dry	0.76	±12%	0.8	±9%
		Moist	0.69	±16%	0.69	±12%

This factor can be applied to estimate the soil carbon stock of areas that have been converted from native conditions and continuously managed for predominantly annual crops over 50 yrs. Land use factor for long-term cultivation represents the change in carbon that occurs after 20 or more years of continuous cultivation.

To take into account of the effect of tillage regime on soil carbon stock, the following stock change factors F_{MG} can be used for Italy, which represents the effect on C stocks at 20 years following the management change. “Full Tillage” is a substantial soil disturbance with full inversion and/or frequent (within year) tillage operations. At planting time, little (e.g., <30%) of the surface is covered by residues. “Reduced tillage” consists in a primary and/or secondary tillage but with reduced soil disturbance (usually shallow and without full soil inversion). Normally leaves surface with >30% coverage by residues at planting. “No-Tillage” is a direct seeding without primary tillage, with only minimal soil disturbance in the seeding zone. Herbicides are typically used for weed control.

Table 3-A. Relative stock change factors (over 20 years) for tillage regime (F_{MG}) in climatic and soil conditions of Italy (from table 5.5 of Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines).

MANAGEMENT (TILLAGE)	temp_regime	moist_regime	Refinement 2019		IPCC 2006	
			F_{MG}	error	F_{MG}	error
Full	Cool/Warm	Dry/Moist	1.00	NA	1.00	NA
Reduced	Cool	Dry	0.98	±5%	NA	NA
		Moist	1.04	±4%	NA	NA
	Warm	Dry	0.99	±3%	1.02	6%
		Moist	1.05	±4%	1.08	5%
NoTill	Cool	Dry	1.03	±4%	NA	NA
		Moist	1.09	±4%	NA	NA
	Warm	Dry	1.04	±3%	1.1	±5%
		Moist	1.10	±4%	1.15	±4%

The land-use factor for long-term cultivation and for tillage regime were updated in refinement 2019 of IPCC guidelines. Data were compiled from published literature based on the following criteria: a) must be an experiment with a control and treatment; b) provide soil organic C stocks or the data needed to compute soil organic C stocks (bulk density, OC content, gravel content); c) provide depth of measurements; d) provide the number of years from the beginning of the experiment to C stock sample collection; and c) provide location information.

There were 303 published studies with 2383 observations for long-term cultivation and perennial tree/woody crops, and 212 published studies with 2046 observations for reduced tillage and no-tillage (References provided at bottom of Table 5.5 at page 28-29 of Chapter 5 of Volume 4 of Refinement 2019 of IPCC guidelines).

Semi-parametric mixed effect models were developed to estimate the new factors (Breidt et al. 2007). Several variables were tested including depth, number of years since the management change, climate, the type of management change (e.g., reduced tillage vs. no-till), and the first-order interactions among the variables. Uncertainty was quantified based on the prediction error for the model, and represents a 95percent confidence interval for each of the factor values. The resulting confidence intervals can be used to construct probability distribution functions with a normal density for propagating error through the calculations.

Finally, the organic matter input stock change factor F_I , was not updated in refinement 2019 of IPCC guidelines 2006, and the values applicable to Italy are summarized in the table here below:

Table 4-A: Relative stock change factors (over 20 years) for organic matter input (F_I) in climatic and soil conditions of Italy (from table 5.5 of Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines)

			Refinement 2019 and IPCC 2006	
ORGANIC INPUT	temp_regime	moist_regime	F_I	Error
Low	Cool/Warm	Dry	0.95	±13%
		Moist	0.92	±14%
Medium	Cool/Warm	Dry/Moist	1.00	NA
HighNoManure	Cool/Warm	Dry	1.04	±13%
		Moist	1.11	±10%
HighWithManure	Cool/Warm	Dry	1.37	±12%
		Moist	1.44	±13%

“Low organic input” occurs when there is removal of residues (via collection or burning), frequent bare-fallowing, production of crops yielding low residues (e.g., vegetables, tobacco, cotton), no mineral fertilization or N-fixing crops.

“Medium organic input” is representative for annual cropping with cereals where all crop residues are returned to the field. If residues are removed then supplemental organic matter (e.g., manure) is added. Also requires mineral fertilization or N-fixing crop in rotation.

“High organic input without manure” represents significantly greater crop residue inputs over medium C input cropping systems due to additional practices, such as production of high residue yielding crops, use of green manures, cover crops, improved vegetated fallows, irrigation, frequent use of perennial grasses in annual crop rotations, but without manure applied.

“High organic input with manure” represents significantly higher C input over medium C input cropping systems due to an additional practice of regular addition of animal manure.

3. Nitrous oxide emissions

The IPCC Tier 1 method (equations 11.1, 11.9, 11.10, Volume 4) assumes that N_2O emissions are directly proportional to the N amount added to the soil, with emission factors specific for N sources and types, and distinct for direct and indirect emission pathways:

- **Direct** N_2O emissions from managed soils that occur through a direct pathway
- **Indirect** N_2O emissions taking place through two indirect pathways: N volatilization/deposition and N leaching

For both direct and indirect N_2O emissions the equations provided by the IPCC guidelines let to estimate the amount of N lost with emissions (N_2O-N amount), which must be converted to N_2O emissions by using the following equation, where 44/28 is the ratio between molecular weights of N_2O and N:

$$N_2O = N_2O-N \bullet 44/28$$

Five levels of N fertilisation, derived from Hijbeek et al. (2017), have been used for trade-offs estimation (0, 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg ha⁻¹), considering synthetic fertilisers (urea-based, nitrate-based, and urea:nitrate mix) and organic fertilisers (animal manure and green manure). To account for the specific emission factors of the fertiliser formulations, we set a 65:35 urea:nitrate ratio when a mixed application of a nitrate and urea-based fertiliser was applied, as from official data of the Italian Institute of Statistics in 2006-2022 (ISTAT, 2023).

Additionally, we accounted for N inputs originating from crop residues, including aboveground and belowground components, and N mineralisation from C loss due to land management change. The same emission factor was applied to animal and green manure, as the IPCC guidelines do not distinguish between the different sources of organic N fertilisers. We complemented direct with indirect N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilised from managed soils (par. 2.2) and N leaching (par. 2.3).

To convert units from kg N₂O-N to Mg N₂O, the values were multiplied by 44/28 (ratio of molecular weights) and 10⁻³. Then, the resulting values were multiplied by 265, i.e., the global warming potential over 100 years (GWP₁₀₀) as of the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (IPCC, 2013), to convert N₂O emissions into Mg of CO₂ equivalent.

3.1 Direct N₂O emissions from managed soils

The main reference equation for calculation of direct N₂O emissions from managed soils in IPCC guidelines in Equation 11.1 (Chapter 11, Volume 4).

In task 5.3 we decided to disregard N₂O emissions from organic soil, as in Italy the presence of these soils is not relevant, and N₂O emissions from grazed soil, as the focus of the project is on cultivated soils. So, the related variables in Equation 11.1 were non considered in this study, as showed in Figure 2-A. Tier 1 methodologies for estimation direct N₂O emissions do not consider variations in land use, soil type, climate, or management practices, but just the amount of nitrogen inputs to soil multiplied per the emission factor EF₁. Moreover, N₂O emissions from N inputs to flooded rice were also disregarded, as rice was not included among the crops object of the study in SOMMIT project.

EQUATION 11.1
DIRECT N₂O EMISSIONS FROM MANAGED SOILS (TIER 1)

$$N_2O_{Direct-N} = N_2O-N_{N_{inputs}} + N_2O-N_{OS} + N_2O-N_{PRP}$$

Where

$$N_2O-N_{N_{inputs}} = \left[\left[(F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{CR} + F_{SOM}) \cdot EF_1 \right] + \left[(F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{CR} + F_{SOM})_{FR} \cdot EF_{1FR} \right] \right]$$

$N_2O-N_{OS} + N_2O-N_{PRP}$

emissions from organic soils and grazed soils

$(F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{CR} + F_{SOM})_{FR} \cdot EF_{1FR}$

N₂O emissions from N inputs to flooded rice

Figure 2-A: Equation for the estimation of direct N₂O emissions from managed soils. In red, emissions excluded from SOMMIT study. Source: chapter 11 volume 4 of 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019)

Four are the nitrogen inputs to soil to be accounted for, expressed as kg N yr⁻¹:

- **F_{SN}** amount of synthetic fertiliser N applied to soils
- **F_{ON}** amount of animal manure, compost, sewage sludge and other organic N additions applied to soils (e.g., rendering waste, guano, brewery waste, etc.).
- **F_{CR}** amount of N in crop residues (above-ground and below-ground), including N-fixing crops, and from forage/pasture renewal, returned to soils annually.
- **F_{SOM}** amount of N in mineral soils that is mineralized, in association with loss of soil C from soil organic matter as a result of changes to land use or management

F_{CR} is estimated from crop yield, default factors for above-/belowground residue: yield ratios and residue N contents, following equation 11.6 of Chapter 11, Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2019). These variables for major crop types are indicated in Table 11.1A of the same chapter.

F_{SOM} is the only SOC stock/ N_2O emissions trade-off variable included in the IPCC guidelines equations for the estimation of N_2O emissions from agricultural soils. It can be estimated after the equation 11.8 reported in Figure 3. Where a loss of soil C occurs, the mineralised N is considered as an additional source of N available for conversion to N_2O . The same default emission factor (EF_1) is applied to mineralised N from soil organic matter loss as is used for direct emissions resulting from fertiliser and organic N inputs to agricultural land.

The opposite process to mineralisation, whereby inorganic N is sequestered into newly formed SOM, is not taken account of in the calculation of the mineralised N source. This is because of the different dynamics of SOM decomposition and formation, and also because reduced tillage in some circumstances can increase both SOM and N_2O emission (Smith and Conen, 2004). Thus, it can be stated that F_{SOM} only partially represent the SOC stock/ N_2O emissions possible trade-off aspects.

EQUATION 11.8
N MINERALISED IN MINERAL SOILS AS A RESULT OF LOSS OF SOIL C THROUGH CHANGE IN LAND USE OR MANAGEMENT (TIERS 1 AND 2)

$$F_{SOM} = \sum_{LU} \left[\left(\Delta C_{Mineral, LU} \cdot \frac{1}{R} \right) \cdot 1000 \right]$$

Where:

- F_{SOM} = the net annual amount of N mineralised in mineral soils as a result of loss of soil carbon through change in land use or management, kg N
- $\Delta C_{Mineral, LU}$ = average annual loss of soil carbon for each land-use type (LU), tonnes C (Note: for Tier 1, $\Delta C_{Mineral, LU}$ will have a single value for all land-uses and management systems. Using Tier 2 the value for $\Delta C_{Mineral, LU}$ will be disaggregated by individual land-use and/or management systems.
- R = C:N ratio of the soil organic matter. A default value of 15 (uncertainty range from 10 to 30) for the C:N ratio (R) may be used for situations involving land-use change from Forest Land or Grassland to Cropland, in the absence of more specific data for the area. A default value of 10 (range from 8 to 15) may be used for situations involving management changes on *Cropland Remaining Cropland*. C:N ratio can change over time, land use, or management practice¹⁷. If countries can document changes in C:N ratio, then different values can be used over the time series, land use, or management practice.

Figure 3-A: Equation for the estimation of F_{SOM} . Source: Chapter 11, Volume 4 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2019)

In Table 5-A are reported the values of the emission factor EF_1 disaggregated by climate (dry/wet) and type of fertilizer (synthetic/organic).

In wet climates, the EF_1 is further disaggregated by synthetic fertiliser N inputs and other N inputs.

2006 version of IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2006) provided a unique value for EF_1 equal to 0,01 with an uncertainty range of 0,003-0.03; the 2019 refinement of the guidelines split this unique value in three different values and reduced the uncertainty.

Table 5-A. Tier 1 emission factors to estimate direct N₂O emissions from managed soils. Source: Table 11.1 chapter 11 volume 4 of 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019)

	Aggreg. value	Uncertainty Range ¹	Disaggregation by climate and fertilizer	Unit	Value	Uncertainty Range ²
EF ₁	0,010	0,001-0,018	Synthetic fertiliser inputs in wet climates (including mixtures that include both synthetic and organic forms of N)	[kg N ₂ O–N (kg N) ⁻¹]	0,016	0,013 - 0,019
			Other N inputs in wet climates (organic amendments, animal manures e.g. slurries, digested manures, N in crop residues and mineralised N from soil organic matter decomposition)		0,006	0,001 - 0,011
			All N inputs in dry climates		0,005	0 - 0,011

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- Rochette, P., Liang, B. C., Pelster, D., Bergeron, O., Lemke, R., Kroebel, R., MacDonald, D., Yan, W. & Flemming, C. (2018) Soil nitrous oxide emissions from agricultural soils in Canada: exploring relationships with soil, crop and climatic variables. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 254: 69-81.

In order to derive these three values all studies from the meta-analysis databases by Stehfest & Bouwman (2006), van Lent et al. (2015), Grace et al. (2016), van der Weerden et al. (2016), Albanito et al. (2017), Cayuela et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2017), and Rochette et al. (2018) were extracted, excluding the following studies: control site not available, non peer-reviewed, different from field studies (laboratory, greenhouse, modelling), conducted in flooded rice fields, related to

¹ Uncertainty range of disaggregated EF₁ based on the 95% confidence interval of fitted values. Uncertainty range of aggregated EF₁ is based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile of the dataset

² Uncertainty range of disaggregated EF₁ based on the 95% confidence interval of fitted values. Uncertainty range of aggregated EF₁ is based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile of the dataset

grazed soils, enhanced synthetic fertilizers or organic fertiliser either treated with inhibitors or coated, conducted on drained organic soils.

The meta-analysis conducted on the selected studies (170 peer reviewed papers concerning 177 study sites and 848 EF₁ observations) is described in **Annex 11A.2** of the 2019 refinement (IPCC, 2019) and in the peer reviewed article by **Hergoualc'h et al. 2021**. Of these reviewed papers, the following eight were included also in the meta-analysis conducted in WP2 of the SOMMIT project:

- Abalos D, Sanz-Cobena A, Garcia-Torres L, van Groenigen J, Vallejo A (2013) Role of maize stover incorporation on nitrogen oxide emissions in a non-irrigated Mediterranean barley field. *Plant Soil* 364, 357–371.
- Alluvione F, Bertora C, Zavattaro L, Grignani C (2010) Nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide emissions following green manure and compost fertilization in corn. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 74, 384–395.
- Kontopoulou CK, Bilalis D, Pappa VA, Rees RM, Savvas D (2015) Effects of organic farming practices and salinity on yield and greenhouse gas emissions from a common bean crop. *Sci. Hortic. Amsterdam* 183, 48–57.
- Meijide A, Díez JA, Sánchez-Martín L, López-Fernández S, Vallejo A (2007) Nitrogen oxide emissions from an irrigated maize crop amended with treated pig slurries and composts in a Mediterranean climate. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 121, 383–394.
- Meijide A, García-Torres L, Arce A, Vallejo A (2009) Nitrogen oxide emissions affected by organic fertilization in a non-irrigated Mediterranean barley field. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 132, 106–115.
- Plaza-Bonilla D, Álvaro-Fuentes J, Arrúe JL, Cantero-Martínez C (2014) Tillage and nitrogen fertilization effects on nitrous oxide yield-scaled emissions in a rainfed Mediterranean area. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 189, 43–52.
- Sánchez-Martín L, Sanz-Cobena A, Meijide A, Quemada M, Vallejo A (2010b) The importance of the fallow period for N₂O and CH₄ fluxes and nitrate leaching in a Mediterranean irrigated agroecosystem. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 61, 710–720.
- Sanz-Cobena A, García-Marco S, Quemada M, Gabriel JL, Almendros P, Vallejo A (2014) Do cover crops enhance N₂O, CO₂ or CH₄ emissions from soil in Mediterranean arable systems?. *Science of the total environment* 466, 164-174.

The meta-analysis by Hergoualc'h et al. 2021 concluded that climate is a major driver of emission, with an EF₁ three times higher in wet climates (0.014, 95% CI 0.011–0.017) than in dry climates (0.005, 95% CI 0.000–0.011). Likewise, the form of the fertilizer markedly modulated the EF₁ in wet climates, where the EF₁ for synthetic and mixed forms (0.016, 95% CI 0.013–0.019) was also almost three times larger than the EF₁ for organic forms (0.006; 95% CI 0.001–0.011). Other factors such as land cover and soil texture, C content, and pH were also important regulators of the EF₁ as showed in table 1 and 2 of Hergoualc'h et al. 2021. The uncertainty associated with the disaggregated EF₁ was considerably reduced as compared to the range in the 2006 IPCC guidelines: for global emissions was estimated a range of 883–1285 Gg N₂O-N using refined emission factors in comparison to a range of 539–2713 Gg N₂O-N computed from the 2006 IPCC GL.

Compared to estimates from the 2006 IPCC EF₁, emissions based on the 2019 IPCC EF₁ range from 15% to 46% lower in countries dominated by dry climates to 7%–37% higher in countries with wet climates and high synthetic N fertilizer consumption.

Direct soil N₂O emissions from global agricultural croplands estimated from the 2019 Refinement were 4% higher than emissions computed from the 2006 IPCC guidelines. Among the top three emitters—China, the United States, and India which all together contribute half of global emissions. China and the United States emissions were, respectively, 21% and 13% higher when estimated from the 2019 IPCC Refinement than from the 2006 IPCC guidelines, a trend particularly pronounced toward the eastern wet areas of those countries. In India, which is predominantly dry, the 2019 Refinement emissions were 21% lower than the 2006 IPCC GL estimates.

Estimated global emissions from synthetic N fertilizer application increased by 27% with the use of the 2019 Refinement as compared to emissions computed from the 2006 IPCC guidelines: wet regions displaying a strong percentage increase and dry regions a strong percentage decrease.

Estimated global emissions from manure application to croplands were almost halved by using the 2019 IPCC Refinement instead of the 2006 IPCC guidelines (−43%), a trend consistent for all countries and slightly more pronounced in dry regions than in wet regions.

For Italy a N₂O emission increase of about +50% from synthetic fertilization, and a N₂O emission reduction of about -30% from organic fertilization is showed in Figure 4-A from Hergoualc'h et al. 2021 (overall N₂O emissions' increase from fertilization of about +35%). It would be interesting to develop more detailed analysis for Italy, spatializing N input to soil and considering differentiated EF₁ depending on climate zone (wet/dry) and type of fertilizer (synthetic/organic).

In 2021 indirect N₂O emissions from managed soils in Italy accounted for about 6% of total agriculture sector's emissions, while direct N₂O emissions accounted for 22%, as reported in the Italian submission to UNFCCC for the year 2023 (Annual European Union greenhouse gas inventory 1990–2021 and inventory report 2023 available at <https://unfccc.int/ghg-inventories-annex-i-parties/2023>); so indirect emissions correspond to about 28% of the direct one.

In the following two sections methodologies to estimate indirect emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilized from managed soils and from N-leaching are described.

Figure 4-A: Percentage difference between direct soil N₂O emissions from global agricultural croplands using the Tier 1 method from the 2019 IPCC Methods Refinement (MR) to the 2006 IPCC National GHG Inventories Guidelines (GL). Source: Hergoualc’h et al. 2021

3.2 Indirect N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilized from managed soils

The same N sources of direct N₂O emissions from managed soils arising from agricultural inputs of N have been considered in the estimate of indirect N₂O emissions (F_{SN} , F_{ON} , F_{CR} , F_{SOM} listed at page); F_{PRP} which is the amount of N (urine and dung) deposited on soil by animals grazing on pasture, range and paddock, is disregarded in the present study.

EQUATION 11.9
N₂O FROM ATMOSPHERIC DEPOSITION OF N VOLATILISED FROM MANAGED SOILS (TIER 1)

$$N_2O_{(ATD)-N} = \left[(F_{SN} \cdot \text{Frac}_{GASF}) + ((F_{ON} + F_{PRP}) \cdot \text{Frac}_{GASM}) \right] \cdot EF_4$$

Figure 5-A: Equation for the estimation of indirect N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilized from managed soils. Source: chapter 11 volume 4 of 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019)

Table 6-A: Values for the estimation of N₂O emissions from N volatilization and redeposition. Source: Table 11.3 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC 2006, IPCC 2019)

Refinement 2019					IPCC 2006	
Default value	Uncertainty range	Disaggreg.	Default value	Uncertainty range	Default value	Uncertainty range
EF₄						
N volatilisation and redeposition [kg N ₂ O–N (kg NH ₃ –N + NO _x –N volatilised) ⁻¹]						
0,010	0,02 – 0,018	Wet climate	0,014	0,011-0,017	0,010	0,002-0,05
		Dry climate	0,005	0,000-0,011		
Frac_{GASF}						
Volatilisation from synthetic fertiliser [kg NH ₃ –N + NO _x –N) (kg N applied) ⁻¹]						
0,11	0,02 – 0,33	Urea	0,15	0,03-0,43	0,10	0,03 – 0,3
		Ammonium-based	0,08	0,02-0,3		
		Ammonium-nitrate-based	0,05	0,00-0,20		
		Nitrate-based	0,01	0,00-0,02		
Frac_{GASM}						
Volatilisation from all organic N fertilisers applied, [kg NH ₃ –N + NO _x –N) (kg N applied) ⁻¹]						
0,21	0,00-0,31	-	-	-	0,2	0,05-0,5

None of the review papers used to update the value of the variables for the estimation of indirect N₂O emissions in the refinement 2019 were also included in the meta-analysis of WP2 of the ΣOMMIT project.

In order to update the values of **EF₄**, the emission factor for indirect N₂O emissions from N deposition, in the refinement 2019, the following review papers were collected from the same sources of EF₁ listed in Table 5-A:

- Aronson, E. & Allison, S. (2012) *Meta-analysis of environmental impacts on nitrous oxide release in response to N amendment. Frontiers in Microbiology* 3.
- Bühlmann, T., Hiltbrunner, E., Korner, C., Rihm, B. & Achermann, B. (2015) *Induction of indirect N₂O and NO emissions by atmospheric nitrogen deposition in (semi-)natural ecosystems in Switzerland. Atmospheric Environment* 103: 94-101.

- *De Vries, W., Kros, J., Reinds, G. & Butterbach-Bahl, K. (2011) Quantifying impacts of nitrogen use in European agriculture on global warming potential. Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability 3(5): 291-302.*
- *Liu, L. & Greaver, T. (2009) A review of nitrogen enrichment effects on three biogenic GHGs: the CO₂ sink may be largely offset by stimulated N₂O and CH₄ emission. Ecology Letters 12(10): 1103-1117.*
- *Van der Gon, H. & Bleeker, A. (2005) Indirect N₂O emission due to atmospheric N deposition for the Netherlands. Atmospheric Environment 39(32): 5827-5838*

The analysis of the studies contained in these review papers, described in Annex 11.A5 of Chapter 11, Volume 4 of 2019 refinement of IPCC guidelines 2006 (IPCC, 2019), revealed similar EF₄ values as EF₁ results; so, it was decided to use the same emission factors as EF₁ for EF₄. Disaggregation was only considered for climate type (see Figure 4-A) due to the absence of dependence of EF₄ upon the form (organic or synthetic) of original N input that volatilized. Methods and data are described in Annex 11A.2 of Chapter 11, Volume 4 of 2019 refinement of IPCC guidelines 2006 (IPCC, 2019). The aggregated EF₄ is the same as the aggregated EF₁, with uncertainty range based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile of the dataset. The disaggregated EF₄ are the same as the EF₁ disaggregated by wet and dry climates, with uncertainty range based on the 95% confidence interval of fitted values.

In comparison with value of EF₄ reported in IPCC guidelines 2006 the Refinement 2019 reduce the uncertainty range of the aggregated value and provide a halved value for dry climates and a slightly higher value for wet climates. So we can expect a reduction of estimated emissions in dry climates and a light increase in wet ones.

Frac_{GASF} is the fraction of nitrogen input to soils (as synthetic fertilizers) which volatilize as NH₃ and NO_x; the guidelines 2006 provide a unique value of this variable equal to 0.1; in the refinement 2019 a review was carried out in order to disaggregate the value of Frac_{GASF} based on the type of fertilizer, weighting world fertiliser usage with number of observations from review papers; more details about the methodology are contained in Annex 11A.7 of Refinement 2019. Uncertainty range was based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile. The analyzed studies were retrieved from the following review papers:

NH₃: Bouwman et al. 2002; Pan et al. 2016.

Bouwman, A. F., Boumans, L. J. M. & Batjes, N. H. (2002) Estimation of global NH₃ volatilization loss from synthetic fertilizers and animal manure applied to arable lands and grasslands. Global Biogeochemical Cycles 16(2): 8-1

Pan, B., Lam, S. K., Mosier, A., Luo, Y. & Chen, D. (2016) Ammonia volatilization from synthetic fertilizers and its mitigation strategies: A global synthesis. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 232(Supplement C): 283- 289.

NO_x: Liu et al. 2017.

Liu, S., Lin, F., Wu, S., Ji, C., Sun, Y., Jin, Y., Li, S., Li, Z. & Zou, J. (2017) A meta-analysis of fertilizer-induced soil NO and combined NO+N₂O emissions. Global Change Biology 23(6): 2520-2532.

The disaggregation in 4 fertilizers categories was based on chemical composition; these four categories are listed here below in decreasing order of volatilization:

Category	Fertilizers included	Frac _{GASF}	Uncertainty range
Ammonium-based	ammonia, ammonium sulphate, ammonium phosphate	0,08	0,02-0,3
Ammonium-nitrate-based	ammonium nitrate, calcium ammonium nitrate, Nitrogen solutions, Other NP-N and NPK compounds	0,05	0,00-0,20
Nitrate-based	N-K compounds	0,01	0,00-0,02

The refinement 2019 provide also an aggregated value of Frac_{GASF} similar to the one of guidelines 2006 (slightly higher with slightly larger uncertainty range).

For the estimate of ΣOMMIT index the disaggregated values were used.

Frac_{GASM} is the fraction of applied organic N fertilizer materials (F_{ON}) and of urine and dung N deposited by grazing animals (F_{PRP}) that volatilizes as NH₃ and NO_x: the guidelines 2006 provide a unique value of this variable equal to 0.2; in the refinement 2019 review papers on NH₃ and NO_x were collected to update the value of Frac_{GASM} which was set at 0.21; details are contained in Annex 11A.8 of Refinement 2019. Uncertainty range, based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile, resulted larger than the one of guidelines 2006. The analyzed studies were retrieved from the following review papers:

- *Bouwman, A. F., Boumans, L. J. M. & Batjes, N. H. (2002) Estimation of global NH₃ volatilization loss from synthetic fertilizers and animal manure applied to arable lands and grasslands. Global Biogeochemical Cycles 16(2): 8-1.*
- *Cai, Y. & Akiyama, H. (2016) Nitrogen loss factors of nitrogen trace gas emissions and leaching from excreta patches in grassland ecosystems: A summary of available data. Science of The Total Environment 572: 185-195.*
- *Liu, S., Lin, F., Wu, S., Ji, C., Sun, Y., Jin, Y., Li, S., Li, Z. & Zou, J. (2017) A meta-analysis of fertilizer-induced soil NO and combined NO+N₂O emissions. Global Change Biology 23(6): 2520-2532.*

For NH₃, the arithmetic mean was calculated from Bouwman et al. (2002) and Cai & Akiyama (2016). For NO_x, the mean and uncertainty range were calculated from Cai & Akiyama (2016) and Liu et al (2017). The difference between mean EF for cattle and sheep excreta were negligible, thus livestock type was not considered. The default Frac_{GASM} was derived as the sum of the arithmetic mean of NH₃ EF and NO_x EF, as showed in Table 8A.1 from Annex 11A.8 of refinement 2019 (IPCC 2019) reported here below:

	n	Mean	Range (2.5 th to 97.5 th percentile)	Source of data
NO _x	40	0.015	0 – 0.149	Liu et al. (2017)
NH ₃	172	0.197	0 – 0.295	Bouwman et al. (2002), Cai & Akiyama (2016)
NO _x + NH ₃	212	0.212	0 – 0.312	References listed above

3.3 Indirect N₂O emissions from N leaching/runoff from managed soils

Here below is reported the equation for the estimation of indirect N₂O emissions from leaching/runoff. Source: chapter 11 volume 4 of 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019).

EQUATION 11.10
N₂O FROM N LEACHING/RUNOFF FROM MANAGED SOILS IN REGIONS WHERE LEACHING/RUNOFF OCCURS (TIER 1)

$$N_2O_{(L)-N} = (F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{PRP} + F_{CR} + F_{SOM}) \cdot \text{Frac}_{LEACH-(H)} \cdot EF_5$$

Table 7-A: Values for the estimation of indirect N₂O emissions from leaching/run-off. Source: Table 11.3 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC 2006, IPCC 2019)

	Refinement 2019		IPCC 2006	
	Default value	Uncertainty range	Default value	Uncertainty range
EF₅ [leaching/runoff], kg N ₂ O–N (kg N leaching/runoff) ⁻¹	0,011	0,000 – 0,02	0,0075	0,0005-0,025
FracLEACH-(H) N losses by leaching/runoff in wet climates, [kg N (kg N additions or deposition by grazing animals) ⁻¹]	0,24	0,01 – 0,73	0,3	0,1 – 0,8

The estimation methodology of **EF₅** is described in Annex 11A.6 of Refinement 2019. A dataset of 254 in-situ observations was retrieved from the review of Tian et al. 2019 containing emission factors of groundwaters (101 observations), rivers and reservoirs (91 observations), estuaries (23 observations):

Tian, L., Cai, Y. & Akiyama, H. (2019) A review of indirect N₂O emission factors from agricultural nitrogen leaching and runoff to update of the default IPCC values. Environmental Pollution 245: 300-306

The dataset on emission factors from rivers includes also non-agricultural N source, including both agricultural (mainly arable farming and grazing grassland) and urban sewage N sources, as it was difficult to separate the different N sources based on the limited information in the publications. Uncertainty range is based on the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile. The value estimated in Refinement 2019 is slightly higher than the one contained in Guidelines 2006, with a reduced uncertainty interval (0,02 vs 0,048).

The estimation methodology of **FracLEACH** is described in Annex 11A.9 of Refinement 2019; it is the arithmetic mean of 355 data observations with uncertainty range for a 95 percent confidence interval, retrieved from the following studies:

Two review papers:

- *Di, H., Cameron, K. Nitrate leaching in temperate agroecosystems: sources, factors and mitigating strategies. Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems 64, 237–256 (2002).*
- *Cai, Y. & Akiyama, H. (2016) Nitrogen loss factors of nitrogen trace gas emissions and leaching from excreta patches in grassland ecosystems: A summary of available data. Science of The Total Environment 572: 185- 195*

Original papers on N leaching/runoff that used lysimeters and in-situ field measurements, excluding studies conducted in the laboratory and studies that used mitigation technologies such as nitrification inhibitor:

- *Moreno, F., Cayuela, J., Fernandez, J., FernandezBoy, E., Murillo, J. & Cabrera, F. (1996) Water balance and nitrate leaching in an irrigated maize crop in SW Spain. Agricultural Water Management 32(1): 71-83.*

- Diez, J., Roman, R., Caballero, R. & Caballero, A. (1997) Nitrate leaching from soils under a maize-wheat-maize sequence, two irrigation schedules and three types of fertilisers. *Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment* 65(3): 189-199.
- Catt, J., Howse, K., Christian, D., Lane, P., Harris, G. & Goss, M. (1998) Strategies to decrease nitrate leaching in the Brimstone Farm Experiment, Oxfordshire, UK, 1988-93: the effect of straw incorporation. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 131: 309-320
- Sogbedji, J., van Es, H., Yang, C., Geohring, L. & Magdoff, F. (2000) Nitrate leaching and nitrogen budget as affected by maize nitrogen rate and soil type. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 29(6): 1813-1820.
- Asadi, M., Clemente, R., Das Gupta, A., Loof, R. & Hansen, G. (2002) Impacts of fertigation via sprinkler irrigation on nitrate leaching and corn yield in an acid-sulphate soil in Thailand. *Agricultural Water Management* 52(3): 197-213.
- Readman, R., Beckwith, C. & Kettlewell, P. (2002) Effects of spray application of urea fertilizer at stem extension on winter wheat: N recovery and nitrate leaching. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 139: 11-25
- Ren, L., Ma, J. & Zhang, R. (2003) Estimating nitrate leaching with a transfer function model incorporating net mineralization and uptake of nitrogen. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 32(4): 1455-1463.
- Dauden, A. & Quilez, D. (2004) Pig slurry versus mineral fertilization on corn yield and nitrate leaching in a Mediterranean irrigated environment. *European Journal of Agronomy* 21(1): 7-19.
- Dauden, A., Quilez, D. & Vera, M. (2004) Pig slurry application and irrigation effects on nitrate leaching in Mediterranean soil lysimeters. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 33(6): 2290-2295.
- Diez, J., Hernaiz, P., Munoz, M., de la Torre, A. & Vallejo, A. (2004) Impact of pig slurry on soil properties, water salinization, nitrate leaching and crop yield in a four-year experiment in Central Spain. *Soil Use and Management* 20(4): 444-450.
- Bakhsh, A., Kanwar, R. & Karlen, D. (2005) Effects of liquid swine manure applications on NO₃-N leaching losses to subsurface drainage water from loamy soils in Iowa. *Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment* 109(1-2): 118-128.
- Basso, B. & Ritchie, J. (2005) Impact of compost, manure and inorganic fertilizer on nitrate leaching and yield for a 6-year maize-alfalfa rotation in Michigan. *Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment* 108(4): 329-341.
- Gehl, R., Schmidt, J., Stone, L., Schlegel, A. & Clark, G. (2005) In situ measurements of nitrate leaching implicate poor nitrogen and irrigation management on sandy soils. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 34(6): 2243-2254.
- Fang, Q., Yu, Q., Wang, E., Chen, Y., Zhang, G., Wang, J. & Li, L. (2006) Soil nitrate accumulation, leaching and crop nitrogen use as influenced by fertilization and irrigation in an intensive wheat-maize double cropping system in the North China Plain. *Plant and Soil* 284(1-2): 335-350.
- Li, C., Farahbakhshazad, N., Jaynes, D., Dinnes, D., Salas, W. & McLaughlin, D. (2006) Modeling nitrate leaching with a biogeochemical model modified based on observations in a row-crop field in Iowa. *Ecological Modelling* 196(1-2): 116-130.
- Diez-Lopez, J., Hernaiz-Algarra, P., Arauzo-Sanchez, M. & Carrasco-Martin, I. (2008) Effect of a nitrification inhibitor (DMPP) on nitrate leaching and maize yield during two growing seasons. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research* 6(2): 294-303.
- Conrad, Y. & Fohrer, N. (2009) Modelling of nitrogen leaching under a complex winter wheat and red clover crop rotation in a drained agricultural field. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth* 34(8-9): 530-540.

- Zhu, B., Wang, T., Kuang, F., Luo, Z., Tang, J. & Xu, T. (2009) Measurements of Nitrate Leaching from a Hillslope Cropland in the Central Sichuan Basin, China. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 73(4): 1419-1426.
- Aronsson, H. & Stenberg, M. (2010) Leaching of nitrogen from a 3-yr grain crop rotation on a clay soil. *Soil Use and Management* 26(3): 274-285.
- Bakhsh, A., Kanwar, R. & Baker, J. (2010) N-Application Methods and Precipitation Pattern Effects on Subsurface Drainage Nitrate Losses and Crop Yields. *Water Air and Soil Pollution* 212(1-4): 65-76.
- Salmeron, M., Caverro, J., Quilez, D. & Isla, R. (2010) Winter Cover Crops Affect Monoculture Maize Yield and Nitrogen Leaching under Irrigated Mediterranean Conditions. *Agronomy Journal* 102(6): 1700-1709.
- Yague, M. & Quilez, D. (2010) Response of Maize Yield, Nitrate Leaching, and Soil Nitrogen to Pig Slurry Combined with Mineral Nitrogen. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 39(2): 686-696.
- Claret, M., Urrutia, R., Ortega, R., Best, S. & Valderrama, N. (2011) Quantifying nitrate leaching in irrigated wheat with different nitrogen fertilization strategies in an Alfisol. *Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research* 71(1): 148-156.
- Huang, M., Liang, T., Ou-Yang, Z., Wang, L., Zhang, C. & Zhou, C. (2011) Leaching losses of nitrate nitrogen and dissolved organic nitrogen from a yearly two crops system, wheat-maize, under monsoon situations. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 91(1): 77-89
- Gallejones, P., Castellon, A., del Prado, A., Unamunzaga, O. & Aizpurua, A. (2012) Nitrogen and sulphur fertilization effect on leaching losses, nutrient balance and plant quality in a wheat-rapeseed rotation under a humid Mediterranean climate. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 93(3): 337-355.
- Perego, A., Basile, A., Bonfante, A., De Mascellis, R., Terribile, F., Brenna, S. & Acutis, M. (2012) Nitrate leaching under maize cropping systems in Po Valley (Italy). *Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment* 147: 57-65.
- Sorensen, P. & Rubaek, G. (2012) Leaching of nitrate and phosphorus after autumn and spring application of separated solid animal manures to winter wheat. *Soil Use and Management* 28(1): 1-11.
- Tafteh, A. & Sepaskhah, A. (2012) Yield and nitrogen leaching in maize field under different nitrogen rates and partial root drying irrigation. *International Journal of Plant Production* 6(1): 93-113.
- Wang, T., Zhu, B. & Kuang, F. (2012) Reducing interflow nitrogen loss from hillslope cropland in a purple soil hilly region in southwestern China. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 93(3): 285-295.

Refinement 2019 simplifies the N leaching fraction to the unique value of 0.24, and $\text{Frac}_{\text{LEACH}}$ only applies to wet climates or to regions where $\Sigma(\text{rain}) - \Sigma(\text{ET0})$ reference evapotranspiration > soil water holding capacity, or where irrigation (except drip irrigation) is used.

To overcome this simplification, for the estimation of N leaching ΣOMMIT trade-off component, $\text{FRAC}_{\text{LEACH}}$ was calculated using the methodology provided by the Grey Water Footprint guidelines (GWF) (Franke et al. 2013) in place of the unique value of 0.24 provided by IPCC Tier 1 methodology, in order to consider a broader range of factors influencing $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ leaching: soil properties (texture, drainage), precipitation, N application rate, N fixation by leguminous crops, crop N uptake and offtake through harvest, and other management practices (Table 8-A). The GWF guidelines attribute a weight (w_i) to each factor, proportional to its impact on N- NO_3 leaching, and assign a leaching potential score (s_i , from 0 to 1) to each state of the factor, and estimate the leaching fraction α as follow:

($\alpha_{min}=0,01$; $\alpha_{avg}=0,1$; $\alpha_{max}=0,25$)

$$\alpha = \alpha_{min} + \left[\frac{\sum_i s_i \times w_i}{\sum_i w_i} \right] \times (\alpha_{max} - \alpha_{min})$$

The values of s and w used in our pilot study are reported in the Table below:

Table 8-A: Factors influencing the leaching potential of nitrogen (elaborated from Franke et al. 2013)

Category	Factor	Weight w	Score s (0-1)				
Environmental factors	Atmospheric N deposition	12	Intermediate				
			0.5				
	Soil Texture class	17	Clay	Silt	Loam	Sand	
			0	0.33	0.67	1	
	Soil natural drainage	12	Clay	Silt	Loam	Sand	
			0	0.33	0.67	1	
Precipitation class (mm)	17	0-600	600-1200	1200-1800	>1800		
		0	0.33	0.67	1		
Agricultural practices	Plant N-fixation (kg ha ⁻¹) Crop type	12	Low fixing leguminous *	High fixing leguminous **	Not leguminous		
			0.67	1	0		
	N application rate (Kg ha ⁻¹)	12	0	50	100	150	>150
			0	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
	Plant uptake (yield percentage)	6	>= 90%	>= 75%	>= 65%	< 65%	
			0	0.33	0.67	1	
	Management practices	12	Till = F Irr= ND Res = R	Till = F Irr= ND Res = B	Till = F Irr= D Res = R	Till = F Irr= D Res = B	
			1	0.9	0.7	0.6	
Till = R/NT Irr = ND Res = R			Till = R/NT Irr = ND Res = B	Till = R/NT Irr= D Res = R	Till = R/NT Irr = ND Res = B		
		0.8	0.7	0.4	0.3		
* bean and green bean, lentil ** pea, chickpea, grain pea, soybean, protein pea Till – soil tillage (F - full, R - reduced, NT - no tillage); Irr - irrigation (ND – non-drip, D – drip); Res – crop residues (R - removed, B - buried);							

Since irrigation is not explicitly considered in the GWF, we assigned 0-600 mm as the precipitation class of a dry climate without irrigation, 600-1200 mm as precipitation class of a dry climate with irrigation, 1600-1800 mm as the precipitation class of a moist climate without irrigation, and >1800 mm as the precipitation class to a moist climate with irrigation. IPCC map of climatic zones (Carre et al., 2010) and the ISPRA’s map of average annual precipitation map relative to the period 1951-2022 (Braca et al 2023) were used to establish a correspondence between the GWF precipitation class and

the IPCC climatic zones, confirming that Italian dry climate zones are characterised by annual precipitation of about 600-900 mm, while moist climate zones by precipitation higher than 1200 mm year⁻¹ (Figure 6-A).

This approach led to obtain a range of values for α included between 0.04 and 0.22 with average 0.13 (coherent with the range of values for $FRAC_{LEACH}$ provided by Refinement 2019 and reported in Table 7-A of this Annex).

Figure 6-A: Comparison between the A) IPCC map of climatic zones and B) the ISPRA's map of average annual precipitation map relative to the period 1951-2022 (Braca et al 2023); these two maps have been used to establish a correspondence between the GWF precipitation class and the IPCC climatic zones.

4. Crop Yield

The crops included in our study (Table 1) were selected based on the availability of coefficients for estimating N content from residues in the 2019 Refinement (IPCC, 2019). Statistical production data were obtained from ISTAT, with yield ($Mg\ ha^{-1}$) calculated as the mean ratio of total production to cultivated areas from 2006 to 2022. To model the response curve of crop yield to N fertilisation levels and types, we employed a non-linear least squares model, fitting data points from the meta-analysis from Hijbeeket al. 2017. We assumed that the indicated N fertilisation levels encompassed mineral and organic components, with their ratio set as in Table 1. Bias and root mean square error (Table 9-A) were calculated to assess the non-linear models' performance. The effect of irrigation on yield has been quantified by considering a crop-specific yield percentage reduction derived from Daryanto et al. (2017).

Table 9-A: Root mean square error (RMSE) of the non-linear least squares model used to fit the response curve of crop yield to N fertilisation levels and types

Crop group	Input	RMSE
Spring cereals	animal manure	9.69
Spring cereals	green manure	6.37
Spring cereals	no	8.60
Potatoes	animal manure	63.54
Potatoes	green manure	41.10
Potatoes	no	58.66
Beans and pulses	animal manure	119.33
Beans and pulses	green manure	75.05
Beans and pulses	no	120.18
Winter cereals	animal manure	10.57
Winter cereals	green manure	13.87
Winter cereals	no	16.85
Winter cereals	animal manure	1.78
Winter cereals	green manure	2.02
Winter cereals	no	2.70
Winter cereals	animal manure	16.62
Winter cereals	green manure	20.36
Winter cereals	no	19.45

5. Uncertainty

The uncertainty in the estimation of trade-off components was based on the 2019 Refinement, which provides 'most likely' values and uncertainty ranges for each emission factor. Since the upper and lower limits of these uncertainty ranges are not symmetrical and given that the 2019 Refinement does not provide information on the probability of distribution functions, we set a triangular probability distribution of errors, using the most likely value as the mode and assuming that upper and lower values comprised 97.5% of the possible values (IPCC 2006). We randomly sampled 1000 values from this distribution using the median absolute deviation to quantify the uncertainty associated with the triangular distribution. We then combined the uncertainties of the emission factors to provide uncertainty estimates for each trade-off component, using the following equations for error propagation provided in chapter 3 of Volume 1 of IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2006):

EQUATION 3.2
COMBINING UNCERTAINTIES – APPROACH 1 – ADDITION AND SUBTRACTION

$$U_{total} = \frac{\sqrt{(U_1 \cdot x_1)^2 + (U_2 \cdot x_2)^2 + \dots + (U_n \cdot x_n)^2}}{|x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n|}$$

Where:

- U_{total} = the percentage uncertainty in the sum of the quantities (half the 95 percent confidence interval divided by the total (i.e., mean) and expressed as a percentage). This term ‘uncertainty’ is thus based upon the 95 percent confidence interval;
- x_i and U_i = the uncertain quantities and the percentage uncertainties associated with them, respectively.

EQUATION 3.1
COMBINING UNCERTAINTIES – APPROACH 1 – MULTIPLICATION

$$U_{total} = \sqrt{U_1^2 + U_2^2 + \dots + U_n^2}$$

Where:

- U_{total} = the percentage uncertainty in the product of the quantities (half the 95 percent confidence interval divided by the total and expressed as a percentage);
- U_i = the percentage uncertainties associated with each of the quantities.

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Annex B: supplementary results from the statistical analysis

Table 10-B: Root mean square error (RMSE) from k-fold cross validation applied in Random Forest models

K-fold	Δ SOC	N ₂ O emissions	NO ₃ leaching	Crop yield
F1	0.222	0.034	1.107	5.643
F2	0.221	0.035	1.093	5.712
F3	0.221	0.035	1.082	5.783
F4	0.226	0.035	1.073	5.664
F5	0.220	0.036	1.101	5.751
Mean	0.222	0.035	1.091	5.711
% Var. explained	97.980	98.700	96.740	99.33

Table 11-B: Link between the cluster variable and the quantitative variables (η^2 tests)

Quantitative variables	η^2	p.value
N ₂ O emissions	0.541	0
NO ₃ leaching	0.505	0
Crop yield	0.761	0
CO ₂ emissions	0.334	0

Table 12-B: Link between the cluster variable and the categorical variables (χ^2 test)

Categorical variables	p.value	df
moisture regime	0.000e+00	2
precipitations	0.000e+01	6
crop	0.000e+02	34
organic N	0.000e+03	4
mineral N	0.000e+04	6
irrigation	0.000e+05	4
N input	0.000e+06	8
OM input	0.000e+07	6
crop residues	0.000	2
soil class	0.000	4
soil tillage	0.000	4
soil texture	0.000	6

Table 13-B: Description of each cluster by quantitative variables; only significant results are shown. A positive or negative v.test indicates a cluster mean significantly higher or lower than the global mean. Variables are ordered by v-test. value

Cluster	Quantitative variables	v.test	Cluster mean	Global mean	Cluster sd	Global sd	p.value
C1	Δ SOC	0,536	0,643	2,694	3,272	0,000	0,536
	N ₂ O emissions	0,373	0,730	0,477	0,698	0,000	0,373
	N-NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	8,376	16,812	9,565	13,637	0,000	8,376
	Crop yield	0,323	0,673	0,203	0,326	0,000	0,323
C2	Crop yield	0,919	0,673	0,089	0,326	0,000	0,919
	N-NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	18,384	16,812	8,796	13,637	0,000	18,384
	Δ SOC	-0,375	0,643	2,626	3,272	0,000	-0,375
C3	N ₂ O emissions	2,183	0,730	0,527	0,698	0,000	2,183
	N-NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	42,086	16,812	12,952	13,637	0,000	42,086
	Δ SOC	6,140	0,643	2,797	3,272	0,000	6,140
	Crop yield	0,816	0,673	0,225	0,326	0,000	0,816

Table 14-B: Description of each cluster by the categorical variables; only significant results are shown. Within-cluster (Mod/Cla) and across-cluster (Cla/Mod) distributions, and global cluster mean of categorical variables are also reported. Variables are ordered by v-test values.

Cluster	Factor	Level	Cla.Mod	Mod.Cla	Global	p.value	v.test
C1	N input	0	97.15	62.75	25.58	0	Inf
	irrigation	no irr	59.07	75.07	50.34	0	Inf
	mineral N	no min N	84.49	64.76	30.36	0	Inf
	organic N	no org N	57.55	81.11	55.82	0	Inf
	precipitations	0-600	52.85	44.61	33.43	3E-264	3E+01
	crop	winter cereal mix	97.92	4.31	1.74	6E-209	3E+01
	crop residues	high	47.55	61.43	51.17	6E-202	3E+01
	crop	spring cereal mix	97.22	4.28	1.74	8E-202	3E+01
	crop	protein pea	97.05	4.27	1.74	4E-200	3E+01
	OM input	medium	48.60	49.94	40.70	3E-168	3E+01
	precipitations	1200-1800	45.92	38.76	33.43	9E-62	2E+01
	crop	bare fallow	91.67	1.35	0.58	3E-52	2E+01
	crop	lentil	58.85	3.46	2.33	2E-27	1E+01
	moisture regime	dry	42.31	53.42	50.00	7E-24	1E+01
	crop	oat	49.39	4.35	3.49	8E-12	7E+00
	crop	field pea	48.70	4.29	3.49	2E-10	6E+00
	crop	grain pea	47.57	4.19	3.49	2E-08	6E+00
	crop	beans and green bean	47.05	4.14	3.49	2E-07	5E+00
	crop	chickpea	46.01	4.05	3.49	7E-06	4E+00
	soil class	HAC	41.17	34.65	33.33	4E-05	4E+00
	crop	rye	45.40	4.00	3.49	5E-05	4E+00
	crop	soybean	34.00	6.99	8.14	4E-10	-6E+00
	crop	maize	34.90	12.29	13.95	1E-12	-7E+00
	crop	sorghum	34.70	12.23	13.95	2E-13	-7E+00
	crop	potato	34.27	12.07	13.95	9E-16	-8E+00
	moisture regime	moist	36.89	46.58	50.00	7E-24	-1E+01
	crop	barley	26.39	4.65	6.98	3E-43	-1E+01
	crop	wheat	26.00	4.58	6.98	9E-46	-1E+01
	crop	durum wheat	25.52	4.50	6.98	5E-49	-1E+01
	N input	50	30.93	15.44	19.77	6E-59	-2E+01
	OM input	high + manure	27.65	10.15	14.53	6E-78	-2E+01
	OM input	high	25.65	9.41	14.53	2E-106	-2E+01
	crop residues	removed	31.28	38.57	48.83	6E-202	-3E+01
	precipitations	600-1200	21.05	8.81	16.57	3E-222	-3E+01
irrigation	drip irr	19.90	8.30	16.52	2E-251	-3E+01	
precipitations	>1800	18.68	7.81	16.57	2E-286	-4E+01	
N input	200	15.22	6.93	18.02	0E+00	-Inf	
N input	150	16.31	7.42	18.02	0E+00	-Inf	
N input	100	15.89	7.46	18.60	0E+00	-Inf	
irrigation	other irr	19.86	16.62	33.14	0E+00	-Inf	
mineral N	urea based	19.87	11.85	23.62	0E+00	-Inf	
mineral N	nitrate based	19.94	11.61	23.07	0E+00	-Inf	
mineral N	balanced	20.32	11.77	22.95	0E+00	-Inf	
organic N	animal manure	17.41	9.71	22.08	0E+00	-Inf	
organic N	green manure	16.46	9.18	22.10	0E+00	-Inf	
C2	N input	150	73.19	26.22	18.02	0E+00	Inf
	irrigation	other irr	68.23	44.95	33.14	0E+00	Inf
	organic N	animal manure	76.92	33.77	22.08	0E+00	Inf
	organic N	green manure	71.06	31.21	22.10	0E+00	Inf
	precipitations	600-1200	78.55	25.87	16.57	0E+00	Inf
	N input	100	70.83	26.20	18.60	7E-286	4E+01
	mineral N	nitrate based	68.00	31.19	23.07	1E-276	4E+01
	mineral N	urea based	66.86	31.39	23.62	3E-249	3E+01
	mineral N	balanced	66.77	30.46	22.95	1E-237	3E+01
	irrigation	drip irr	69.73	22.90	16.52	1E-221	3E+01
OM input	high + manure	70.50	20.37	14.53	2E-206	3E+01	

	N input	200	68.04	24.38	18.02	1E-204	3E+01
	moisture regime	dry	57.45	57.10	50.00	4E-149	3E+01
	OM input	high	61.98	17.91	14.53	4E-69	2E+01
	N input	50	59.05	23.20	19.77	2E-56	2E+01
	crop residues	removed	54.74	53.13	48.83	7E-56	2E+01
	crop	durum wheat	62.80	8.71	6.98	7E-36	1E+01
	precipitations	>1800	57.91	19.08	16.57	5E-35	1E+01
	crop	wheat	62.59	8.68	6.98	1E-34	1E+01
	crop	barley	62.20	8.63	6.98	1E-32	1E+01
	crop	soybean	57.07	9.23	8.14	2E-13	7E+00
	crop	maize	54.19	15.03	13.95	1E-08	6E+00
	crop	potato	54.12	15.01	13.95	2E-08	6E+00
	soil class	HAC	52.03	34.47	33.33	1E-05	4E+00
	crop	sorghum	53.04	14.71	13.95	6E-05	4E+00
	soil tillage	no till	51.67	34.42	33.52	4E-04	4E+00
	soil tillage	full	48.93	32.13	33.03	4E-04	-4E+00
	crop	beans and green bean	44.97	3.12	3.49	2E-04	-4E+00
	crop	grain pea	43.49	3.02	3.49	2E-06	-5E+00
	crop	field pea	42.80	2.97	3.49	2E-07	-5E+00
	crop	oat	42.27	2.93	3.49	3E-08	-6E+00
	precipitations	0-600	46.99	31.23	33.43	1E-17	-9E+00
	crop	lentil	34.38	1.59	2.33	2E-19	-9E+00
	OM input	low	43.98	26.43	30.23	8E-52	-2E+01
	crop residues	high	46.08	46.87	51.17	7E-56	-2E+01
	crop	bare fallow	0.00	0.00	0.58	3E-59	-2E+01
	OM input	medium	43.62	35.29	40.70	3E-90	-2E+01
	moisture regime	moist	43.16	42.90	50.00	4E-149	-3E+01
	crop	protein pea	0.00	0.00	1.74	7E-178	-3E+01
	crop	spring cereal mix	0.00	0.00	1.74	7E-178	-3E+01
	crop	winter cereal mix	0.00	0.00	1.74	7E-178	-3E+01
	precipitations	1200-1800	35.85	23.82	33.43	2E-306	-4E+01
	N input	0	0.00	0.00	25.58	0E+00	-Inf
	irrigation	no irr	32.13	32.15	50.34	0E+00	-Inf
	mineral N	no min N	11.53	6.96	30.36	0E+00	-Inf
	organic N	no org N	31.56	35.02	55.82	0E+00	-Inf
	moisture regime	moist	19.94	98.83	50.00	0E+00	Inf
	precipitations	1200-1800	18.22	60.38	33.43	2E-248	3E+01
	precipitations	>1800	23.41	38.45	16.57	6E-229	3E+01
	Crop residues	removed	13.98	67.68	48.83	2E-118	2E+01
	OM input	Low	16.07	48.14	30.23	4E-116	2E+01
	N input	200	16.73	29.89	18.02	4E-70	2E+01
	mineral N	urea based	13.27	31.06	23.62	3E-25	1E+01
	mineral N	balanced	12.92	29.38	22.95	1E-19	9E+00
	N input	100	13.28	24.49	18.60	5E-19	9E+00
	soil tillage	full	11.92	39.02	33.03	2E-14	8E+00
	irrigation	other irr	11.91	39.11	33.14	2E-14	8E+00
	organic_n	green manure	12.48	27.34	22.10	5E-14	8E+00
	soil class	VOL	11.82	39.05	33.33	3E-13	7E+00
	soil texture	sand	12.08	29.92	25.00	1E-11	7E+00
	soil class	WET	11.65	38.48	33.33	5E-11	7E+00
	mineral N	nitrate based	12.06	27.58	23.07	2E-10	6E+00
	OM input	high	12.38	17.83	14.53	3E-08	6E+00
	organic_n	no org N	10.89	60.26	55.82	5E-08	5E+00
	crop	sorghum	12.26	16.96	13.95	3E-07	5E+00
	crop	potato	11.61	16.06	13.95	3E-04	4E+00
	soilTexture	clay	8.33	20.65	25.00	5E-10	-6E+00
	crop	protein pea	2.95	0.51	1.74	4E-11	-7E+00
	crop	spring cereal mix	2.78	0.48	1.74	1E-11	-7E+00
	crop	winter cereal mix	2.08	0.36	1.74	2E-14	-8E+00

irrigation	no irr	8.80	43.91	50.34	5E-15	-8E+00
soil tillage	no till	8.22	27.31	33.52	4E-16	-8E+00
OM input	medium	7.78	31.36	40.70	9E-32	-1E+01
soil class	HAC	6.80	22.48	33.33	3E-47	-1E+01
organic N	animal manure	5.66	12.39	22.08	3E-51	-2E+01
crop residues	high	6.37	32.32	51.17	2E-118	-2E+01
OM input	high + manure	1.85	2.67	14.53	2E-128	-2E+01
mineral N	no min N	3.98	11.97	30.36	4E-152	-3E+01
N input	0	2.85	7.23	25.58	7E-180	-3E+01
precipitations	600-1200	0.40	0.66	16.57	2E-236	-3E+01
precipitations	0-600	0.15	0.51	33.43	0E+00	-Inf
moisture regime	dry	0.24	1.17	50.00	0E+00	-Inf

Table 15-B: Parameters used to build the fuzzy-logic membership functions

Trade-off component	Membership function	Function shape	Parameter	Value
Δ SOC – N ₂ O emissions N-NO ₃ ⁻ leaching ₃	low	Sigmoid	cross slope height	0.33 -25 1
	medium	Gaussian	mean sd	0.5 0.145
	high	Sigmoid	cross slope height	0.67 25 1
Yield	low	Sigmoid	cross slope height	0.53 -35 1
	medium	Gaussian	mean sd	0.7 0.145
	high	Gaussian	mean sd	1 0.11
Σ i	very low	Gaussian	mean sd	0 0.11
	low	Gaussian	mean sd	0.25 0.101
	medium	Gaussian	mean sd	0.5 0.11
	high	Gaussian	mean sd	0.75 0.101
	very high	Gaussian	mean sd	1 0.11

Annex C: description of the three narratives developed to test the Σ ommit index sensitivity

Σ OMMIT index survey

The EJP-Soil Σ OMMIT project aims to develop a trade-off evaluation index, i.e., the Σ OMMIT index, to identify the best farming practices for system productivity, carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions, and nitrate leaching across various pedo-climatic conditions.

The index enables experts and users to embed their perceptions by assigning weights to the relative contribution of crop yield, N₂O emissions, CO₂ sequestration, and NO₃- leaching in defining the trade-offs.

We kindly ask you to read the three short storylines and assign a weight to the relative contribution of the four trade-off components to the index. Please note that the sum of weights in each storyline must be 100.

Lastly, we kindly ask you to complete the table on the last page.

Note:

The estimated time for survey completion is 10 minutes.

The survey results will be used solely for scientific purposes and presented in an anonymous and aggregated format. • • •

We are a collective of young farmers. We share a common vision: to revive and innovate the rural economy of our region, which has been severely tested by the impact of COVID-19 and the intensifying challenges of climate change.

Our primary objective is to produce high-quality and healthy food while fostering soil ecosystem services and ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the process. We strive to obtain certifications and public incentives recognizing and rewarding our

commitment to regenerative agricultural practices. This is precisely why we are intrigued by the potential of adopting the Σ OMMIT Index. By leveraging this tool, we believe we can effectively showcase our work, enhance yields, quantify our real impact on agroecosystems' health, and demonstrate to consumers and public authorities the actual value of our food production.

trade-off components	weight
CO ₂ sequestration	
N ₂ O emissions	
NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	
Crop yield	
<u>Total</u>	<u>100</u>

We are a research and development unit of a multinational agricultural chemical company. We aim to develop solutions that reduce the environmental impact of agrochemicals and fertilizers on soil, water, and air quality. With a farmer-centric approach and strong emphasis on product stewardship, we seek methods to minimize fertilizer

application, optimize nitrogen use efficiency, and improve irrigation, pest, and disease control.

As a forward-thinking technology partner, we are exploring the integration of tools like the $\Sigma OMMIT$ index into our operational pipelines. This enables us to quantify the benefits associated with our services and convey to farmers that we are not merely greenwashing but that our work effectively contributes to more resilient farming systems.

trade-off components	weight
CO ₂ sequestration	
N ₂ O emissions	
NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	
Crop yield	
<u>Total</u>	<u>100</u>

We are the national agency of an EU Member State responsible for allocating CAP funds to farmers. Our mission is to ensure the successful achievement of the environmental and climate goals outlined in the CAP. We actively promote practices that mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and enhance soil conservation. To assist farmers in adopting these practices, we offer financial incentives, personalized technical assistance, and knowledge-

sharing initiatives.

We recognize the importance of tools like the *ΣOMMIT index* to monitor the progress made by farmers with respect to CAP policy objectives. This will allow us to allocate targeted financial support to incentivize farmers to transition toward conservative and regenerative farming practices.

trade-off components	weight
CO ₂ sequestration	
N ₂ O emissions	
NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	
Crop yield	
<u>Total</u>	<u>100</u>

